

Report for Schmidt Ocean Institute's RV *Falkor (too)* + ROV *SuBastian*

Expedition Fkt230602

Octopus Odyssey - Part 1

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Table of Contents

Summary	5
Cruise objectives and importance of doing this work:	5
Geographical area	6
Table 1. Information of seafloor features visited on Fkt230602.	6
Figure 0. Cruise track of Fkt230602 (from R2R)	6
Summary of science operations:	7
Table 2. Overview of Fkt230602 operations	8
Table 3. Overview of all ROV Dives on Fkt230602	9
Table 4. SuBastian dive numbers when various experiments were deployed on the seafloor, for collection in December 2023.	9
Figure 1. Overview of all of the dive sites of Fkt230602 overlain on previously and newly acquired multibeam bathymetry data.	10
Initial findings and potential impact of the research:	11
Table 5. Brief dive highlights from each dive	12
How will information be shared:	13
Acknowledgements, Funding, and Permissions	13
Personnel	14
Dive Summaries:	17
Figure 2. Example dive basket configuration for Fkt230602 dives.	17
Dive S0529 - Dorado Outcrop #1	18
Dive S0530 - Dorado Outcrop #2	22
Dive S0531 - unnamed outcrop SW of Fuente	25
Dive S0532 - Fuente Seamount	28
Dive S0533 - Tengosed Seamount #1	30
Dive S0534 - Tengosed Seamount #2	32
Dive S0535 - unnamed outcrop E of Caballito #1	34
Dive S0536 - Unnamed outcrop east of Caballito #2	36
Dive S0537 - Dorado Outcrop #3	43
Dive S0538 - Unnamed outcrop east of Caballito #3	48
Dive S0539 - Caballito #1	52
Dive S0540 - Caballito #2	55
Dive S0541 - Tengosed #3	57
Dive S0542 - Dorado Outcrop #4	61
Daily plans	65
Biology/Animal Specimen Summary	72
Samples	72
Table 6. Taxonomic groupings of primary biological specimens collected (not including associates).	72
Transects and video annotation	73

Table 7. List of video transects from Fkt230602	74
Table 8. Summary of video files and estimated time lengths from ROV SuBastian dives available on Tator Cloud	75
Figure 3. Example of localization drawing on Tator platform	76
Octopus specimen collection and microbiome sampling	76
Table 9. Summary of cephalopod samples collected on the expedition.	77
Figure 4. Photographs of cephalopod specimens	79
Rock Sample summary	83
Table 10. Rock Samples Descriptions (by Beth Orcutt)	84
Table 11. Smear slides from sediments inside rock samples (by Maria Isabel Sandoval)	85
Sediment Sample summary	88
Table 12. Overview of sediment push cores collected for various analyses, with sample numbers for various analyses.	89
Squeezer Sample summary	91
Table 14. Squeezer Samples collected on Fkt2310602	91
Deployments & Recoveries summary	93
OsmoSamplers	93
Figure 5. OsmoSamplers recovered on Fkt230602	93
Figure 6. OsmoSamplers deployed on Fkt230602	94
Microbe Colonization Experiments (aka Microbe Traps)	95
Table 15. Overview of Microbial Colonization Experiment deployments	95
Figure 7. Example of Microbe Colonization Experiments being deployed at Dorado Outcrop.	96
Figure 8. Overview of assembly of Microbe Colonization Experiments.	97
Figure 9. View of microbe colonization experiments on ROV SuBastian.	98
Figure 10. Microbial colonization experiments at the seafloor	99
Multibeam summary	100
Figure 11. Screenshots of multibeam survey planning lines	100
Heat Flow and Temperature Logger summary	101
Table 16. Temperature logger deployment information	102
Table 17. Summary of heat flow measurements.	103
Figure 12. Preliminary results of heat flow measurements on unnamed outcrop SW of Fuente	104
Figure 13. Preliminary results of heat flow measurements on Fuente seamount.	105
Figure 14. Preliminary results of heat flow measurements on outcrop east of Caballito.	106
Figure 15. Preliminary results of heat flow measurements on Caballito outcrop.	107
Oceanographic observations and Hydrographic/Water sampling (i.e. CTD Niskin rosette casts, ADCP, EK80)	108
Figure 16. Map of the thirteen full-depth CTD locations on Fkt230602	109
Figure 17. Temperature-Salinity Diagram of Stations 1 -13	110

Figure 18 - CTD001	111
Figure 19 - CTD002	112
Figure 20 - CTD003	113
Figure 21 - CTD004	114
Figure 22 - CTD005	115
Figure 23 - CTD006	116
Figure 24 - CTD007	117
Figure 25 - CTD008	118
Figure 26 - CTD009	119
Figure 27 - CTD010	120
Figure 28 - CTD011	121
Figure 29 - CTD012	122
Figure 30 - CTD013	123
Figure 31 - Summarized results from ADCP	124
Figure 32 - Summarized results from altimetry data (AVISO).	125
Table 18. ROV Niskin water samples collected	127
Outreach	129
Artists at Sea	129
Figure 33. Carlos Hiller (background) and Michel Droge (foreground) were Artists-At-Sea on the Octopus Odyssey Fkt230602 expedition.	129
Figure 34. Both artists created numerous paintings during the expedition.	129
Michel Droge	130
Table 19. Nine paintings created © Michel Droge 2023, on temporary loan to Jorge Cortes for exhibit in Costa Rica.	130
Table 20. Watercolors and sketches © Michel Droge 2023	132
Carlos Hiller	134
Table 21. Paintings created © Carlos Hiller 2023.	134
Blogs	135
Livestream and social media engagement	136
Video Products	136
Ship to Shore Engagements	137
Table 22. Ship-to-Shore engagements during Fkt230602	138
Notable Press	139
Ship tours during demobilization	140
Table 23. Tour guests from Costa Rica during Fkt230602	140
Capacity Sharing & Best Practices Research	141

Summary

Cruise objectives and importance of doing this work:

Seamount ecosystems support highly diverse animal communities on the seafloor and the surrounding ocean, yet the diversity, connectivity and ecosystem services of these environments is poorly understood. This knowledge gap confounds efforts to delineate areas in need of conservation management and protection. The Pacific Ocean margin of Costa Rica contains a range of seamount habitats, from the rough terrain of the southwestern margin to the more sparse terrain of the northwest margin. While the southwestern terrain has previously been surveyed (including by RV *Falkor*) and some seamount areas here are already protected, far less is known about the ecosystems of the northwestern terrain. In 2013/2014 very unique animal behaviors and hydrothermal venting were discovered on a small seamount in the northwestern terrain. Namely, extensive aggregations of octopus were observed at a place called the Dorado Outcrop, located in areas of diffuse venting of slightly warmed hydrothermal fluids. At the time of discovery, it was unclear if these aggregations could be considered nurseries, since no viable eggs were observed with brooding mothers. Subsequently, similar behaviors were observed on the Davidson Seamount offshore California, and these aggregations were confirmed to be octopus nurseries.

On this shakedown cruise of the new RV *Falkor (too)*, our international team planned to return to this area to determine the extent of these unique animal behaviors in the region to inform their possible conservation and protection. Moreover, the team planned to use multidisciplinary approaches to determine linkages between fluid-rock alteration, microbial processes, and microbe-animal symbioses at these seamounts, as well as to broader seafloor-ocean coupling in the region. Embedded throughout the research program were elements for enabling capacity development for early career researchers and capacity sharing with scientists from the Group of Latin American and Caribbean Countries. Such activities included remote telepresence-enabled engagement of participants in a deep-sea expedition leadership program, hands-on training for shipboard early career scientists, and specimen collection for regional museums. Likewise, the expedition planned to offer a dual-language outreach program designed to raise awareness amongst Costa Rican and regional audiences of deep-sea conservation issues in the region. Moreover, expedition scientists planned to translate science findings for relevant policy makers, including the Ministry of Environment in Costa Rica and the International Seabed Authority. Collectively, the research, capacity development and outreach goals of the expedition will contribute to objectives of the UN Decade for Ocean Science for Sustainable Development and offer a significant platform for engagement as Costa Rica co-sponsors the third UN Ocean Conference in 2024.

Geographical area

The Fkt230602 Octopus Odyssey expedition was the third shakedown expedition of the RV *Falkor (too)*. The expedition targeted an area of ancient volcanoes on the Cocos Plate offshore Costa Rica, with the goal of exploring the relationship between low-temperature hydrothermal venting and octopus brooding, and for understanding biodiversity and ecosystem function more broadly. Our dive plan targeted six seafloor features (Table 1, Figure 0), five of which had never been explored prior to this expedition. Four of these features have published names – Dorado Outcrop, Tengosed Seamount, Fuente Seamount, and Caballito; however, none of these features have official names in GEBCO. Fuente Seamount overlaps with a region officially known as Guardian Bank that is a common long-line fishing area.

Table 1. Information of seafloor features visited on Fkt230602.

Name used on expedition	Lat.	Lon.	Summit (m)	# dives	Venting?
Dorado Outcrop	9.0816	-87.0972	2980	4	Yes (max 12°C)
Tengosed Seamount	9.1333	-86.9500	1900	3	Yes (max 3°C)
Fuente Seamount	8.8083	-87.1792	2580	1	no
Unnamed outcrop SW of Fuente	8.7417	-87.2083	3090	1	no
Caballito Seamount	8.6138	-87.3263	2850	2	no
Unnamed outcrop E of Caballito	8.8217	-87.2796	2820	3	Yes (max 7°C)

Figure 0. Cruise track of Fkt230602 (from R2R)

Summary of science operations:

From 2-21 June 2023, we conducted 14 dives with ROV *SuBastian* to explore these seafloor features, augmented by 13 full-water-column CTD Niskin Rosette casts and six multibeam surveys (Table 2, Figure 1). We had roughly 229 hours of ROV operations in the water (172 hours on the seafloor + 57 hours of ascent/descent; Table 3), resulting in 208 hours of video and 483 video files (all connected to Tator for video annotation). The longest ROV dive was approximately 35 hours and the deepest depth of ROV exploration was 3178 m. We had 285 sampling events during the ROV dives: 150 primary biological specimens (plus associates), 66 sediment push cores, 28 ROV Niskin samples of bottom water, 13 squeezer fluid samples, 30 rock samples. This also included deployments of 22 different experiments planned for recovery in December 2023, and recovery of 2 experiments from the Dorado Outcrop deployed in 2014. We also conducted 31 video transects.

Two established third-party technologies were used on the expedition: (1) a heat-flow probe for measuring thermal gradients in sediment (provided by shore-based scientist Dr. Andrew Fisher of UCSC), and (2) custom “squeezer” syringe samplers for sampling hydrothermal springs (provided by shore-based scientist Dr. Geoff Wheat of the University of Alaska Fairbanks). We conducted 38 heat flow measurements and thirteen squeezer samplers were correctly collected (in addition to misfires). In addition, a diversity of third-party experiments were deployed on the seafloor, including autonomous temperature loggers, microbial colonization experiments (i.e. microbe traps), two types of animal shelters (i.e. clay pots and PVC joints), OsmoSamplers, and bags of wood. In total, twenty experiments were deployed (Table 4).

Table 2. Overview of Fkt230602 operations

			0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23												
May	29	Mon																																				
May	30	Tue									symposium at UCR																											
May	31	Wed									transport				mobilization																							
June	1	Thu	mobilization																		transit to site																	
June	2	Fri					CTD1 trench			transit continued												CTD2																
June	3	Sat	Dor.	ROV Dive #1 - 529 - Dorado																		CTD3 HydroMidN																
June	4	Sun	ROV Dive #2 - 530 - Dorado																																			
June	5	Mon		MB - Fuente		CTD4			ROV Dive #3 - 531 - SW Fuente																													
June	6	Tue	dive 531 continued										multibeam Fuente						ROV Dive #4																			
June	7	Wed	dive 532 - Fuente continued																																			
June	8	Thu	dive continued						transit for mid-cruise event - cancelled										multibeam Fuente																			
June	9	Fri							ROV Dive #5 - 533 - Tengosed												CTD5 HydroN																	
June	10	Sat	transit						ROV Dive #6 - 534 - Tengosed												multibeam - Caballito																	
June	11	Sun							ROV Dive #7 - 535 - Unnamed E Caballito												CTD6 HydroSW																	
June	12	Mon	CTD7 Cab.		ROV Dive #8 - 536 - Unnamed E Caballito																																	
June	13	Tue	transit for medical evacuation																																			
June	14	Wed																			ROV Dive #9 - 537 - unnamed E Caballito																	
June	15	Thu	CTD8 HydroCen		ROV Dive #10 - 538 - unnamed E of Caballito												multibeam																					
June	16	Fri	Caballio						ROV Dive #11 - 539 - Caballito												multibeam																	
June	17	Sat	Caballio						ROV Dive #12 - 540 - Caballito																													
June	18	Sun	CTD9 HMS		ROV Dive #13 - 541 - Tengosed												CTD10 Tengo.																					
June	19	Mon	ROV Dive #14 - 542 - Dorado (+ hull inspection)																																			
June	20	Tue	CTD11 HMW		CTD12 HME			Transit to port										CTD13 Trench2		transit continued																		
June	21	Wed													ship tour groups																							
June	22	Thu													demobilization																							

Table 3. Overview of all ROV Dives on Fkt230602

Dive ID	Location	Deck to Deck	Deployment	Descent	Seabed	Ascent	Recovery	Max Depth	Samples	
S0529	Dorado Outcrop	00d 16:26:44	00d 00:08:48	00d 02:16:46	00d 11:42:01	00d 02:01:58	00d 00:17:08	3175.77m	28	
S0530	Dorado Outcrop	00d 19:38:22	00d 00:08:06	00d 02:19:18	00d 14:48:15	00d 02:00:29	00d 00:22:12	3171.26m	28	
S0531	Unnamed outcrop SW of Fuente Seamount	01d 01:15:42	00d 00:07:42	00d 02:26:07	00d 19:55:53	00d 02:14:04	00d 00:31:54	3156.87m	20	
S0532	Fuente Seamount	01d 10:26:39	00d 00:05:11	00d 02:21:06	01d 05:41:12	00d 02:00:33	00d 00:18:36	3178.22m	21	
S0533	Tengosed Seamount	00d 12:17:06	00d 00:10:21	00d 01:43:49	00d 08:49:36	00d 01:17:37	00d 00:15:40	2277.58m	23	
S0534	Tengosed Seamount	00d 12:21:59	00d 00:07:06	00d 01:32:00	00d 08:55:27	00d 01:29:19	00d 00:18:05	2054.23m	18	
S0535	Unnamed Outcrop East of Caballito	00d 11:58:50	00d 00:24:01	00d 02:09:55	00d 07:11:43	00d 01:57:11	00d 00:15:58	2960.48m	16	
S0536	Unnamed Feature East of Caballito	00d 10:53:32	00d 00:12:13	00d 02:08:52	00d 06:08:07	00d 02:07:50	00d 00:16:28		7	
S0537	Dorado Outcrop	00d 11:46:57	00d 00:07:12	00d 02:12:48	00d 07:05:44	00d 02:04:33	00d 00:16:38	3001.03m	19	
S0538	Unnamed Outcrop East of Caballito	00d 15:59:26	00d 00:08:28	00d 02:01:29	00d 11:13:14	00d 02:14:52	00d 00:21:22	2934.69m	29	
S0539	Caballito Seamount	00d 16:21:17	00d 00:06:52	00d 02:16:17	00d 11:32:52	00d 02:04:45	00d 00:20:27	3151.56m	18	
S0540	Caballito	00d 16:31:17	00d 00:06:59	00d 02:18:17	00d 11:29:16	00d 02:15:15	00d 00:21:28	3156.44m	23	
S0541	Tengosed Seamount	00d 15:38:31	00d 00:18:04	00d 01:43:12	00d 11:48:00	00d 01:29:13	00d 00:20:00	2135.75m	17	
S0542	Dorado Outcrop	00d 17:24:12	00d 00:29:51	00d 02:14:17	00d 11:49:42	00d 02:23:56	00d 00:26:24	3090.85m	18	
Totals	14 Dives	09d 21:00:40	00d 02:41:02	01d 05:44:20	07d 04:11:09	01d 03:41:41	00d 04:42:26	3178.22m	285	0

Table 4. SuBastian dive numbers when various experiments were deployed on the seafloor, for collection in December 2023.

Site	Marker	T logger	Microbe Trap	Clay Shelters	PVC shelters	Osmo Sampler	Wood Bag
Dorado	A	542	542				
"	D			529			
"	R	537	529/537		529		
"	W	537	530	530	530	537	530
"	nodule		530				
E of Caballito	Q	536	536			538	538
Tengosed	X	541					
TOTALS	n.a.	5	5	4 (2x ea)	4 (2x ea)	2	2

Figure 1. Overview of all of the dive sites of Fkt230602 overlain on previously and newly acquired multibeam bathymetry data.

Initial findings and potential impact of the research:

Our biggest finding is the confirmation that tiny Dorado Outcrop in Costa Rica's Pacific waters hosts an octopus nursery with hundreds of *Muusoctopus* species brooding viable eggs in low-temperature (12°C) hydrothermal fluids (Table 5). This refutes a previous hypothesis that eggs are not viable in this area¹. We also located a second site of low temperature (maximum temperature recorded was ~7°C) hydrothermal venting with brooding octopus on an unnamed outcrop that was explored for the very first time on this expedition. This is only the world's fifth-known deep-sea octopus nursery associated with hydrothermal springs and the second site found in Costa Rica (the other three being two sites surrounding the Davidson Seamount and one site offshore British Columbia discovered a few days before). On several dives, we witnessed the first moments of life of deep-sea baby octopus of the *Muusoctopus* species releasing from their eggs. We also observed the rapidity with which predators like shrimp and cutthroat eels descend on unprotected octopus eggs, demonstrating how well octopus mothers protect their eggs during the brooding period. Only one species of octopus – the *Muusoctopus* – appears to show the behavior of brooding eggs in warmed waters; the other octopuses we have observed, two unnamed species of *Muusoctopus* and an unnamed species of *Graneledone*, did not exhibit this behavior. During the expedition we carefully observed a variety of octopus behaviors, and we collected several specimens to allow their identification, study population biology and animal microbiomes.

We also discovered a skate (*Bathyraja spinosissima*) nursery at the summit of Tengosed seamount that was explored for the first time on this expedition, confirmed by collection of a skate egg with an embryo. This is one of the deepest living of all known skate species. The association of this nursery with local hydrothermal venting is currently unknown. These deep-sea octopus and skate nurseries exhibit all of the characteristics of Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems and Ecologically and Biologically Sensitive Areas: they are unique and rare, they are required for the survival of these populations, they contain sensitive species slow to recover from disturbance, they have high productivity, and they are relatively pristine. Observations of octopus and skate nurseries on this expedition was synergistic with similar discoveries on seamounts of the Northeast Pacific NEPDEP expedition by Department of Fisheries and Oceans Canada, which was occurring at the same time as Octopus Odyssey.

There were several notable developments related to understanding regional hydrogeology. We confirmed local low-temperature hydrothermal discharge on Tengosed seamount where recharge is also occurring - something that had been predicted but never verified before. We also confirmed low-temperature discharge at another site (unnamed feature east of Caballito) and documented cool heat flow around Caballito, suggesting that this is another site of recharge. Exploration of Fuente Seamount did not reveal local discharge, but exploration at this site was limited by long-line fishing pressure.

On many of these seamounts, we observed unexpected geological features, where millions-of-years-old layers of sediment are exposed at the seafloor, interspersed with the

¹ [Hartwell et al. 2018](#)

basaltic rock formations. Some of these sediment deposits are also coated in mineral crusts. Sediment and crust samples that we collected will be used to further understand sediment origins and histories. Notably, many of the mineral encrusted rock samples collected on the expedition were confirmed to be consolidated sediments, not altered basalts. This may challenge prior interpretations of “basalt” features on the Dorado Outcrop².

150 deep-sea biological specimens were collected to enrich the collection of the Museum of Zoology at the University of Costa Rica and to fuel scientific discovery. The most collected taxonomic groups included echinoderms (n=39), octocorals (n=37), cephalopods (n=25), sponges (n=25) and crustaceans (n=22). In addition, 31 video transects were completed for quantitative analysis of biodiversity. They are the first-ever collections from this seamount region offshore Costa Rica. It is likely that many of the specimens we collected represent new species and new records of known species for the regions. Some of the notable collections included recovery of *Xyloplax* echinoderms and several black coral specimens. Some of the outcrops and seamounts are separated by just a few kilometers, but we have observed different assemblages of organisms on them. This indicates a high diversity and uniqueness of each area. More studies are needed to evaluate how unique the organisms in this small portion of the ocean floor are compared to other deep areas in the region and farther away.

Table 5. Brief dive highlights from each dive

Dive	Location	Highlight
529	Dorado	Confirmation of viable <i>Muusoctopus</i> sp. octopus eggs and nursery
530	Dorado	Collection of octopus & eggs
531	SW Fuente	Sea cucumbers, tripod fish, potentially new octopus species
532	Fuente	Carbonate cliff, acorn worms, dumbo octopus
533	Tengosed	Discovery of skate nursery, high coral & sponge diversity
534	Tengosed	Confirmation of local discharge at recharging seamount
535	E Caballito	Confirmation of elevated heat flow
536	E Caballito	Discovery of new vent site + nursery
537	Dorado	OsmoSampler recovery & deployment
538	E Caballito	Characterization of new vent site (Marker Q)
539	Caballito	Confirmation of cool heat flow, encrusted whale rostrum
540	Caballito	Confirmation of <i>Granelldone</i> octopus brooding outside of venting

² [Wheat et al. 2019](#)

541	Tengosed	Deployment of temperature logger at Marker X vent site
542	Dorado	Numerous locomoting octopus, xyloplax echinoderms

How will information be shared:

Communication of findings is a major objective of the Octopus Odyssey expeditions. Outreach to local communities and managers includes preparing an invited summary of the expedition and importance of deep-sea research, in Spanish, for distribution to the Costa Rican Ministry of Foreign Affairs. This was completed on 10 October, led by Sergio Cambronero. In addition, the team is planning a science symposium in June 2024 in Costa Rica to share findings of the expedition. Data will be made available on BCO-DMO under the program page for the Crustal Ocean Biosphere Research Accelerator (COBRA), which is a US National Science Foundation-funded program: <https://www.bco-dmo.org/program/856233>

Acknowledgements, Funding, and Permissions

Permission to conduct international Marine Scientific Research in Costa Rica's waters was given diplomatic consent by the Costa Rican Ministry of Foreign Affairs to the US Embassy (DNS-2023-0126). This basic research was conducted with the permission to access genetic and biochemical elements and resources of biodiversity or associated traditional knowledge given by the National Commission for the Management of Biodiversity (Comisión Nacional para la Gestión de la Biodiversidad, CONAGEBIO) of the Ministry of Environment and Energy (Ministerio de Ambiente y Energía, MINAE) of Costa Rica (Permit R-026-2023-OT-CONAGEBIO to Dr. Jorge Cortés-Núñez). We also acknowledge the prior informed consent of the Minister of Fisheries and Aquaculture, Mr. Heiner Méndez Barrientos of the Costa Rican Institute of Fisheries and Aquaculture (INCOPECA). **All publications and presentations should reference this permit information.** All specimens are archived at the Museum of Zoology at the University of Costa Rica. Shiptime for this expedition was generously provided by the Schmidt Ocean Institute. Third-party funding for the science party to participate in this expedition came from a variety of sources, including from the Crustal Ocean Biosphere Research Accelerator (COBRA) network funded by the US National Science Foundation (OISE-2114593), discretionary funding of the Bigelow Laboratory for Ocean Sciences, and support from the Blue Nature Alliance. We also thank the following organizations for supporting participation of science party members: Bates College (Michel Droge), California State University of Los Angeles (Gustavo Ramírez), European Union's Horizon 2020 program Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 101038095 and the ATLANTIDA project NORTE-01-0145-FEDER-000040 (Miguel Semedo), Field Museum (Janet Voight), the Maxwell/Hanrahan Foundation (Holly Lutz), Temple University (Emily Cowell), University of Calgary (Rachel Lauer and Rob Perrin), Universidad de Costa Rica, and Universidad Nacional. The science party thanks Esteban Herrera Herrera and Nathalie Swain-Diaz for shipboard assistance with specimen processing and photography, respectively.

Personnel

This third shakedown cruise of the RV Falkor (too) had a “science party” of 18 academic professionals + 2 artists-at-sea + 1 berth of opportunity for a CR govt agency representative + 1 multimedia correspondent + 1 visiting journalist + a large supporting group of academics from shore. Within the academic team, 39% participants were from Costa Rican institutions, 34% were from US institutions, 11% were from Canada, and 16% were from institutions in other countries (Germany, Portugal, Trinidad).

TEAM

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^ = Career Stage: A, Artist; E, early career professional; G, graduate student; P, Postdoc; S, senior scientist

Artists at Sea:

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Carlos Hiller	A	Underwater murals	CRI - independent	info@carloshiller.com

Berth of Opportunity:

Esteban Herrera Herrera	O	Director, Cocos	CRI - SINAC	esteban.herrera@sinac.go.cr
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Shorebased science party:

Fkt230602 Cruise Report

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Dive Summaries:

Figure 2. Example dive basket configuration for Fkt230602 dives.

Starboard side (left): UCSC heat flow probe (not visible), slurp sampler on shelf with hose on basket, temperature probe. Basket outboard L to R: divided milkcrate with squeezers, divided milkcrate for rocks, two coral quivers, small biobox with divider, “Excaliber” measuring and poking stick, and tube for suction sampler. Basket inboard L to R: Six coral quivers, Large BioBox, open milkcrate with nets and scoops. Port side: open shelf with Niskin triggers, rail with 8 push core quivers, 6 Niskin bottles (not visible)

Dive S0529 - Dorado Outcrop #1

Date: 3 June 2023

Time on bottom: 11 hours 42 minutes

of samples collected: 26

Divestream links: [Part 1](#), [Part 2](#)

Dive track: Overview of dive track (white line) and waypoints (grey flags) for the dive. Not all waypoints were visited.

Overview: The highlight of this dive was the confirmation of viable baby octopus! This dive started in the sedimented abyssal plain to the SW of Dorado Outcrop (WP1) for conducting heat flow measurements and sediment push coring. Three heat flow measurements were made. We then transited to the summit of the outcrop to visit the Marker D/G area (WP2) and Marker K/R/W (WP3) area, which were places of known venting. It was very easy to find these former locations, with little overgrowth on the markers. Venting was confirmed, with similar temperatures as have been measured before (max 12.01 at Marker R). The area had many more octopus than were observed in December 2013 and December 2014. A male and female octopus specimen were collected, in addition to eggs. Two OsmoSamplers deployed in 2014 were located though not recovered. Four animal shelters were deployed, and one microbial exposure experiment. There were collections of several other target fauna. This dive ended after completing objectives.

Notable events:

Date & Time	Event	Image
2023-06-03 16:41	Possible octopus copulation at WP2 Marker D	
2023-06-03 18:25	Deployment of clay pot animal traps at Marker D (max temp 8.5°C)	
2023-06-03 18:48	Collection of male octopus	
2023-06-03 19:04	Collection of brooding female and eggs	

Fkt230602 Cruise Report

<p>2023-06-03 19:24</p>	<p>Eels eating octopus eggs at WP2 (they showed up within minutes of collection)</p>	A close-up photograph of a reddish-brown eel on a dark, algae-covered seabed. The eel is positioned over a cluster of small, white, spherical octopus eggs.
<p>2023-06-03 20:03</p>	<p>View of ~200 octopus around WP3 (Marker K/W/R area) and 2014 OsmoSamplers at WP3</p>	A wide-angle photograph of a dark seabed covered with numerous small, blueish-purple octopus. Several yellow markers and a white OsmoSampler are visible on the seabed.
<p>2023-06-03 20:13</p>	<p>First observation of free-swimming baby octopus at WP3</p>	A photograph of a dark seabed with a small, white, free-swimming baby octopus visible in the upper right. Other octopus are visible on the seabed.
<p>2023-06-03 20:15</p>	<p>Shrimp eating octopus eggs and grabbing baby octopus</p>	A close-up photograph of a shrimp eating octopus eggs. The shrimp is positioned over a cluster of white, spherical octopus eggs.

<p>2023-06-03 20:18</p>	<p>The baby octopus got away from the shrimp!</p>	An underwater photograph showing a baby octopus, which is small and pale, positioned near a dark metal lattice structure. The background is dark with some faint light spots.
<p>2023-06-03 21:29</p>	<p>Deployment of microbe traps and animal shelters at Marker R for recovery in December</p>	An underwater photograph showing a complex arrangement of scientific equipment. A prominent yellow bag is visible, along with various tubes, white containers, and other gear. The background is dark and filled with many small, light-colored organisms, possibly jellyfish or similar marine life.

Dive S0530 - Dorado Outcrop #2

Date: 4 June 2023

Time on bottom: 14 hours 15 minutes

of samples collected: 33

Divestream links: [Part 1](#), [Part 2](#)

Dive track: Overview of Dive S0530 track (white line) and way points.

Overview: The highlight of this dive was the collection of several octopus and eggs along with the 2014 “White” OsmoSampler from Marker W. The dive started with video transects in the abyssal plain area. Heat flow measurements did not work on this dive due to positioning. On the outcrop, the majority of operations focused on Markers W and K. Two squeezer samples were collected. Four animal shelters, one microbial exposure experiment, and one wood exposure experiment was deployed. There were collections of several other target fauna. This dive ended after completing objectives.

Notable events:

Date & Time	Event	Image
2023-06-04 10:17	Ctenophore in the water column	
2023-06-04 16:35	Deployment of Microbe Traps on nodule area for recovery in December	
2023-06-04 20:32	Octopus collection with OsmoSampler at Marker W	
2023-06-04 20:44	Attempted Octopus collection, but it got away	

Fkt230602 Cruise Report

<p>2023-06-04 20:57</p>	<p>Deploy Animal Shelters 4x at Marker W for recovery in December</p>	An underwater photograph showing a ROV arm with a gripper mechanism positioned over a rocky seabed. Several purple and white animal shelters are scattered on the rocks. A white marker with the number '3' is visible on the left.
<p>2023-06-04 21:41</p>	<p>Squeezer samples at Marker K/W along with Animal Shelters</p>	An underwater photograph showing a ROV arm with a squeezer tool positioned over a rocky seabed. Several purple and white animal shelters are scattered on the rocks. A white marker with the number '2' is visible in the center.
<p>2023-06-04 22:54</p>	<p>Deploy Microbe and Wood Exposure Experiments at Marker W for recovery in December</p>	An underwater photograph showing a ROV arm with a gripper mechanism positioned over a rocky seabed. Several yellow and white microbe and wood exposure experiments are scattered on the rocks. A white marker with the number '4' is visible on the left.
<p>2023-06-05 00:50</p>	<p>Larger octopus near Marker E, collected at 01:09</p>	An underwater photograph showing a large, light-colored octopus resting on a rocky seabed. The octopus is positioned near a white marker with the number '5'.

Dive S0531 - unnamed outcrop SW of Fuente

Date: 5 June 2023

Time on bottom: 19 hours 55 min

of samples collected: 20

Divestream links: [Part 1](#), [Part 2](#), [Part 3](#)

Dive track in blue line versus planned way points. Dive began to the NE for heat flow, crossed over feature then explored southern section where octopus were observed, then continued heat flow line to the SW.

Overview: The highlights of this dive were the density and diversity of sea cucumbers, some amazing sightings of tripod fish, and observations of several octopus including a potentially new species. This dive focused on conducting heat flow measurements and exploring for venting on an unnamed feature SW of Fuente Seamount. The dive approached the feature from the NE along a line trending NE-SW, crossed over the feature, and then diverted to explore for venting along the southern section before finishing with a few additional heat flow measurements on the western side of the feature. Between each heat flow station, a standard photographic transect of the seafloor was made. 11 heat flow measurements were made, and mildly elevated heat flow was measured, but it is about 1/5th of the gradient as at Dorado. No venting was detected. Several octopus were observed on the southern section, including with viable eggs, though the octopus were not in high density and not associated with any detectable venting. Beaked whale rostrum observed. This dive ended after completing objectives.

Notable events:

Date & Time	Event	Image
2023-06-06 01:30	Beaked whale rostrum	
2023-06-06 03:16	Skate and tripod fish (tripod fish also seen at 2023-06-05 23:37)	
2023-06-06 06:14	Sea cucumber collection	

Fkt230602 Cruise Report

<p>2023-06-06 08:45</p>	<p><i>Graneledone</i> octopus with eggs</p>	
<p>2023-06-06 09:07</p>	<p>Octopus egg collection, viable embryos. Cutthroat eels showed up within minutes to eat eggs.</p>	
<p>2023-06-06 10:18</p>	<p>Sea cucumber</p>	

Dive S0532 - Fuente Seamount

Date: 7 June 2023

Time on bottom: 1 day 5 hours 42 min

of samples collected: 21

Divestream links: [Part 1](#), [Part 2](#), [Part 3](#), [Part 4](#)

Dive track: Dive track (blue line) compared to planned waypoints.

Overview: The highlights of this dive were discovery of a 10m tall cliff of carbonate ooze covered with 20cm thick manganese oxide encrusted blocks (which were later determined to be mudstones) around **WP18**, the observation of a dumbo octopus, and many acorn worms. This 4+ km transect dive aimed to explore various features of Fuente Seamount, since prior heat flow measurements suggested that this could be a site of discharge or recharge. Three heat flow measurements were made at the base of the seamount, but no significantly warm or cool heat flow was detected. No venting was detected. The summit was covered with exposures of indurated carbonate ooze coated with a 10s of centimeter of thick black crusty layer, first observed as a small “table” and then more dramatically as cliffs. The cliffs had few attached fauna. Only a few octopus observed in the 4+ km transect, one of which was collected. This dive ended after completing objectives.

Notable events:

Date & Time	Event	Image
2023-06-07 12:46	First sighting of what appeared to be a crusty basalt sheet flow on top of carbonate. Subsequent analysis indicates that the crusty stuff is oxides over indurated siltstone, with carbonate ooze below.	
2023-06-07 23:44	Carbonate cliff	
2023-06-08 00:29	Dumbo octopus on a flat sedimented area	
2023-06-08 06:44	Octopus collection	

Dive S0533 - Tengosed Seamount #1

Date: 9 June 2023

Time on bottom: 8 hours 49 minutes

of samples collected: 23

Divestream links: [Part 1](#), [Part 2](#)

Dive track: The dive followed a prominent summit cliff edge over some wash out zones.

Overview: The highlight of this dive was discovery of a skate egg collection at the summit of the seamount (WP8), although there was no obvious sign of venting. This dive focused on trying to find evidence of venting areas on Tengosed. None was detected. At deeper depths, “snowdrop” bell-shaped Euplectellidae sponges were numerous, as well as polychaete worm tubes on the exteriors of pillow basalts. Several corals and sponges were collected. This dive ended after completing objectives.

Notable events:

Date & Time	Event	Image
2023-06-09 13:16	skate	
2023-06-09 16:01	Polychaete worm tubes on pillow basalts, with sample of bell sponge (SITCAM view)	
2023-06-09 16:14	Pacific White Skate	
2023-06-09 21:24	Example of skate eggs (a.k.a. mermaid purses) near a pink bubblegum coral	

Dive S0534 - Tengosed Seamount #2

Date: 10 June 2023

Time on bottom: 8 hours 55 minutes

of samples collected: 18

Divestream links: [Part 1](#), [Part 2](#)

Dive track: The dive followed a different summit ridge scarp to the west of the prior dive, ending at the same summit site.

Overview: **The highlight of this dive was the discovery of a site of local discharge on Tengosed Seamount, which is also a site of recharge into basement - this is the first ever (to our knowledge) confirmation of local circulation within a seamount.** The discharge location was near WP2, in a collapse feature surrounded by the “crusty ledge over ooze” material we have observed on most other seamounts. The maximum temperature we could measure was 3.22°C (ambient 1.8°C), although the depth of the venting orifice was hard to reach below the vehicle. Unfortunately squeezer sampling was not successful on this dive. The dominant lithology of the dive was the crusty ledge over ooze, with more rubble basalt at the summit. We again observed the skate egg nursery at the summit, and eggs collected from this dive did have viable embryos in them of different stages of development. Two octopus spotted on dive. Large spiral siphonophore observed in water column on recovery. This dive ended after completing objectives.

Notable events:

Date & Time	Event	Image
2023-06-10 16:27	venting	
2023-06-10 21:25	Skate eggs	

Dive S0535 - unnamed outcrop E of Caballito #1

Date: 11 June 2023

Time on bottom: 7 hours 11 minutes

of samples collected: 16

Divestream links: [Part 1](#)

Dive track: Overview of dive track over the unnamed feature E of Caballito. The dive focused on a saddle near the summit for collecting heat flow perpendicular to a line of prior ship-based heat flow survey. Towards the end of the dive we summited a small peak on the west side.

Overview: The highlight of this dive was confirming elevated heat flow (300+ mW per meter squared) on this seafloor feature, although no venting was detected. Nine heat flow measurements were taken in the sedimented saddle. Several sea cucumber specimens were collected during transits, and one *Graneledone* octopus was observed. The western summit had huge ropey columns of lava and pillow lavas, but no venting was detected. A pod of pilot whales visited the ship in the afternoon. This dive ended after completing objectives.

Notable events:

Date & Time	Event	Image
2023-06-11 14:27	Observation of two sea cucumbers attached (male and female?) - these were sampled	
2023-06-11 19:22	<i>Graneledone</i> octopus observed	

Dive S0536 - Unnamed outcrop east of Caballito #2

Date: 12 June 2023

Time on bottom: 6 hours 8 min

of samples collected: 7

Divestream links: [Part 1](#)

Dive track: Overview of dive progress along waypoints on the southern flank and summit of the unnamed feature east of Caballito. WP1 began in pillow lavas, then transitioned into the “crusty ledge over ooze” textures seen on other seamounts, with low fauna density. Near WP5, fractures and holes in the seafloor began to appear, with slightly warmed temperatures. Continuing along the fracture led to discovery of a small area with venting and octopus aggregations, just below the summit.

Overview: The highlight of this dive was the discovery of the second location of low-temperature hydrothermal venting (max temp 6.79°C) with an octopus nursery in this region! This venting area is just below the summit, and the summit is covered in Stolinifera. At Marker Q, a temperature logger and microbial colonization experiment were deployed quickly after documenting the site, as the dive needed to be terminated early due to need for a medical evacuation. Transit back to port diverted due to military ships in the area.

Notable events:

Date & Time	Event	Image
2023-06-12 13:22	Octopus in view when first on seafloor - a good omen! Pillow lavas at WP1	
2023-06-12 14:17	Bony-eared assfish (summoned from breakfast)	
2023-06-12 14:21	Example of crusty over ooze between WP1 and WP5	
2023-06-12 15:54	Back into pillow basalts at WP5, with first evidence of venting at 3.08°C	

Fkt230602 Cruise Report

<p>2023-06-12 16:21</p>	<p>Squeezer #9 at 3.08°C site location</p>	
<p>2023-06-12 16:32</p>	<p>Temperature measurement in holes in crust near summit (max temp 4.1°C)</p>	
<p>2023-06-12 16:47</p>	<p>Other venting holes (max 4.98°C) with evidence of prior brooding</p>	
<p>2023-06-12 17:02</p>	<p>Discovery of venting and nursery on a vertical wall!</p>	

Fkt230602 Cruise Report

<p>2023-06-12 17:06</p>	<p>View of shimmering orifice on vertical wall with lots of cement</p>	
<p>2023-06-12 17:11</p>	<p>First sighting of second vent site with octo aggregation, which will become Marker Q</p>	
<p>2023-06-12 17:12</p>	<p>View of how tiny Marker Q vent site is</p>	
<p>2023-06-12 17:31</p>	<p>Temperature measurement at what will become Marker Q, max temp 6.79°C</p>	

Fkt230602 Cruise Report

<p>2023-06-12 17:36</p>	<p>View of octopus</p>	
<p>2023-06-12 18:11</p>	<p>Octopus collection</p>	
<p>2023-06-12 18:17</p>	<p>Cutthroat eel attacking eggs within minute of mom being moved</p>	
<p>2023-06-12 18:20</p>	<p>Rock collection at Marker Q, with egg cement</p>	

Fkt230602 Cruise Report

<p>2023-06-12 18:42</p>	<p>Deployed T logger (768604) for recovery in December</p>	
<p>2023-06-12 18:49</p>	<p>Vent shrimp collection</p>	
<p>2023-06-12 19:03</p>	<p>Deployed microbial colonization experiment after deploying Marker Q for recovery in December</p>	
<p>2023-06-12 19:10</p>	<p>Post-collection fly over, showing Marker Q</p>	

Fkt230602 Cruise Report

<p>2023-06-12 19:25</p>	<p>Octo sign-off</p>	
<p>2023-06-12 20:32</p>	<p>Pelagic cephalopod (japatella) for collection</p>	

Dive S0537 - Dorado Outcrop #3

Date: 14 June 2023

Time on bottom: 7 hours 5 min

of samples collected: 19

Divestream links: [Part 1](#)

Dive track: The dive focused on work in the Marker K/R/W area on the southern end of Dorado Outcrop.

Overview: The highlights of this dive were the recovery of a 2014 OsmoSampler from Marker R (which had attached octopus) and deployment of a new OsmoSampler at Marker W. Animal shelter clay pots that had previously been deployed at Marker W were repositioned to allow positioning of the OsmoSampler intake. A temperature logger (768616) and microbe trap experiment were also deployed at Marker R.

Notable events:

Date & Time	Event	Image
2023-06-14 18:27	Max temp at Marker W 10.4°C	
2023-06-14 18:36	Squeezer sample 166 at Marker W	
2023-06-14 18:50	Deployment of OsmoSampler W at Marker W for recovery in December	
2023-06-14 19:44	Deployment of Temperature Logger A at Marker W (view of shrimp attacking exposed eggs)	

<p>2023-06-14 19:16</p>	<p>View of all deployments left at Marker W for recovery in December</p>	An underwater photograph showing a variety of scientific equipment and markers scattered on a dark, rocky seafloor. The equipment includes a white PVC trap, a yellow marker, and several other pieces of gear. The scene is dimly lit, with some light reflecting off the equipment.
<p>2023-06-14 19:55</p>	<p>Recovery of OsmoSampler at Marker W (notes: intake had been moved into basket on earlier dive, attempted to collect male octopus on outside but hid in back of ROV basket)</p>	An underwater photograph showing a ROV basket being lowered or recovered near a marker. The basket is suspended by a yellow crane. A white marker with the letter 'R' is visible in the background. The seafloor is covered with numerous purple and white organisms, likely sea urchins.
<p>2023-06-14 20:50</p>	<p>Temperature measurement in PVC trap (colonized?) at Marker R 3.52°C</p>	
A close-up underwater photograph of a white PVC trap. The trap is tilted, and a specimen, possibly a small octopus or squid, is visible inside. A yellow marker is visible in the background.		
<p>2023-06-14 21:02</p>	<p>Temperature measurement in vent near PVC trap at Marker R 12.2°C</p>	An underwater photograph showing a ROV near a vent and a PVC trap. The ROV is positioned over a vent, and a white PVC trap is visible nearby. A yellow marker with the letter 'R' is also present. The seafloor is covered with numerous purple and white organisms.

Fkt230602 Cruise Report

<p>2023-06-14 21:13</p>	<p>Squeezer sample 169 at Marker R</p>	A close-up view of a ROV's manipulator arm holding a squeezer device over a dark rock surface covered with numerous purple, star-shaped sponges. A white bucket containing a sample is visible to the right.
<p>2023-06-14 21:20</p>	<p>Squeezer 170 in background seawater near Marker R</p>	A wider view showing the ROV's manipulator arm and various cables in the foreground. In the background, a squeezer device is visible in the dark seawater near the rock surface.
<p>2023-06-14 21:39</p>	<p>Deployment of Temperature Logger 768616 ROVitB at Marker R</p>	The ROV's manipulator arm is shown deploying a temperature logger (ROVitB) onto the rock surface. The surrounding area is covered with purple sponges, and a white bucket is visible on the right.
<p>2023-06-14 21:45</p>	<p>Deployment of Microbe Traps at Marker R</p>	The ROV's manipulator arm is shown deploying microbe traps onto the rock surface. The traps are small, white, and attached to yellow strings. The surrounding area is covered with purple sponges, and a white bucket is visible on the right.

<p>2023-06-14 22:13</p>	<p>Overview of deployments left at Marker R (note: T logger repositioning after this)</p>	
<p>2023-06-14 23:07</p>	<p>Reposition Temperature logger at Marker R</p>	
<p>2023-06-14 23:08</p>	<p>Octopus glamor shots 30-minute session</p>	

Dive S0538 - Unnamed outcrop east of Caballito #3

Date: 15 June 2023

Time on bottom: 11 hours 13 min

of samples collected: 29

Divestream links: [Part 1](#), [Part 2](#)

Dive track: S to N look of the unnamed outcrop east of Caballito. The dive began at the summit for sampling and deployments (WP1), then moved down slope along the trend of prior shipboard heat flow to WP2 to make additional measurements. WP2 was actually a small outcrop of rock. Note that transit to this site from Dorado was delayed due to diversion around long-line fishing gear over Fuente area.

Overview: **The highlight of this dive was the deployment of the several experiments at the Marker Q venting site.** Four heat flow measurements were made to the south of the summit.

Notable events:

Date & Time	Event	Image
2023-06-15 13:56	View of octopus below Marker Q, showing broken egg sacs. Max temp 6.15°C	
2023-06-15 14:16	Squeezers 185 at vents just below Marker Q	
2023-06-15 14:30	Osmo glamor shot 30-min session	
2023-06-15 15:15	Temperature measurement at Marker Q max 7.03°C (in hole to the right of the T logger deployed on prior dive)	

Fkt230602 Cruise Report

<p>2023-06-15 15:23</p>	<p>Squeezer 186 at Marker Q in 7.03°C hole</p>	
<p>2023-06-15 16:04</p>	<p>Deployment of Pink OsmoSampler at Marker Q in 7.03°C hole</p>	
<p>2023-06-15 16:35</p>	<p>Deployment of wood experiment at Marker Q</p>	
<p>2023-06-15 16:37</p>	<p>View of deployments at Marker Q for recovery in December</p>	

Fkt230602 Cruise Report

<p>2023-06-15 22:11</p>	<p>Random barnacles on random outcrop along transect</p>	A photograph showing a close-up view of a dark, textured rock surface covered with numerous small, light-colored barnacles. The lighting is somewhat dim, highlighting the irregular shapes and textures of the organisms.
<p>2023-06-16 02:15</p>	<p>Collection of midwater octopus specimens</p>	A photograph of a single, glowing red octopus specimen against a dark background. The octopus is oriented vertically, with its head at the top and its tentacles visible at the bottom. The red glow is concentrated in the central body and tentacles.

Dive S0539 - Caballito #1

Date: 16 June 2023

Time on bottom: 11:32

of samples collected: 18

Divestream links: [Part 1](#), [Part 2](#)

Dive track: View of the first dive on Caballito, starting in sedimented abyssal plain to the east and moving upslope to the summit. Once waypoints were completed, dive continued along summit. Long line fishing gear was immediately to our east for the entire dive, and multibeam mapping over the site the night before had to be offset due to lines in the water.

Overview: The highlight of this dive was confirmation that heat flow at the base of the outcrop is cooler than average lithospheric, which indicates that this is a site of recharge. Nine heat flow measurements were made, with photo transects between waypoints. While pillow basalts were encountered at the steep flanks of the outcrop, the summit was covered in a bright white carbonate ooze covered with a dusting of light brown sediment, with some sediment nodules. Notable collections included an encrusted whale rostrum, a humongous sea cucumber, a rusty can, and a radiolarian. No octopus observed.

Notable events:

Date & Time	Event	Image
2023-06-16 17:51	Carbonate ooze ledge observed	An underwater photograph showing a dark, rocky ledge covered in a light-colored, porous carbonate ooze. The surrounding seafloor is a uniform, dark grey color.
2023-06-16 22:33	Huge sea cucumber collected	A photograph taken from an ROV showing a large, purple sea cucumber lying on the seafloor. A robotic arm is visible on the left side of the frame, and various cables and equipment are visible in the foreground.
2023-06-16 23:31	Beaked whale rostrum with primnoid coral collected	A photograph showing a dark, elongated beaked whale rostrum lying on the seafloor. Next to it is a white, branching primnoid coral. A white starfish is also visible to the left of the coral.
2023-06-17 00:03	Metal can collected for microbiome study	A close-up photograph of a metal can that has been collected. The can is heavily encrusted with bright orange and white microbial growth, likely a type of coral or sponge.

Fkt230602 Cruise Report

2023-06-17 01:35	Radiolarian collected	
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Dive S0540 - Caballito #2

Date: 17 June 2023

Time on bottom: 11 hours 29 minutes

of samples collected: 23

Divestream links: [Part 1](#), [Part 2](#), [Part 3](#), [Part 4](#)

Dive track: Perspective of today's dive (right track) in relation to yesterday's track (left). Started again in sedimented abyssal plain and moved upslope. Once hitting depth with prominent pillow basalts, around 2930 m, followed that contour-ish to see if there was evidence of flow in the rocks (there wasn't).

Overview: **The highlight of this dive was observation of Graneledone octopus brooding eggs.** Six heat flow measurements were made with transects in between. One Muusoctopus specimen was collected, and one pelagic cephalopod was collected.

Notable events:

Date & Time	Event	Image
2023-06-17 19:00	Graneledone octopus	A photograph of a Graneledone octopus, characterized by its white, gear-like suckers, resting on a dark, rocky seabed covered in green algae.
2023-06-17 20:28	Muusoctopus - this one was collected - may be different than the one at Dorado	A close-up photograph of a Muusoctopus, showing its purple body and numerous white, bulbous suckers.
2023-06-17 23:05	Graneledone brooding octopus	A photograph of a Graneledone brooding octopus, showing its white, gear-like suckers and pale body, resting on a dark, rocky seabed.
2023-06-18 00:51	Dumbo octopus in water column after coming off bottom	A photograph of a Dumbo octopus, showing its pinkish-red body and large, ear-like fins, swimming in a dark water column.

Dive S0541 - Tengosed #3

Date: 18 June 2023

Time on bottom: 11 hours 48 mins

of samples collected: 17

Divestream links: [Part 1](#), [Part 2](#)

Dive track: South to North view of Tengosed seamount showing the dive track starting on a little coral-covered pinnacle of rock on the southern summit that had not been visited before (WP1), documentation of the pillow-to-crusty-ledge transition (WP2), then transit to the local discharge site (WP3), return to the skate nursery site and nearby summit to see if there was any evidence of venting, then exploration of ridge to the north. Note that transit to this site and launch of dive were delayed due to long-line fishing activity in the area.

Overview: **The highlights of this dive were the return to the crater discovered on dive 534 to deploy an extended buoy temperature logger for recovery in December (and new Marker X), return to the skate park on the summit, observation of a chimera, discovery of some unknown animal (arrow worm? specimen escaped 😞) dangling from strings under rock ledges, and collection of one octopus specimen.** There were many black corals on this dive.

Notable events:

Date & Time	Event	Image
2023-06-18 14:36	Lots of corals at WP1	
2023-06-18 15:12	Lots of corals at WP2	
2023-06-18 16:20	Crater hole on Tengosed, to be named Marker X	
2023-06-18 16:42	Deployment of temperature logger and Marker X at discharge site (3.22°C on Dive 534, but could not get good measurement on this dive, though entire crater was warmed to 2.34°C compared to ambient of 2.25°C)	

Fkt230602 Cruise Report

<p>2023-06-18 16:44</p>	<p>View of collapsed ledge near Marker X crater</p>	
<p>2023-06-18 16:46</p>	<p>Overview of crater with Marker X</p>	
<p>2023-06-18 19:27</p>	<p>Skate eggs at the skate park (did a transect)</p>	
<p>2023-06-18 21:30</p>	<p>Weird animals (arrow worms??) on gossamer threads under ledge (sampled but lost)</p>	

Fkt230602 Cruise Report

<p>2023-06-18 22:45</p>	<p>Chimera</p>	
<p>2023-06-19 00:29</p>	<p>Observation of baby octopus being released from clutch without provocation</p>	

Dive S0542 - Dorado Outcrop #4

Date: 19 June 2023

Time on bottom: 11 hours 49 minutes

of samples collected: 18

Divestream links: [Part 1](#), [Part 2](#)

Dive track: Overview of the dive track over the northern end of Dorado Outcrop, starting at Marker A region and then heading south

Overview: **The highlights of this dive were confirming 11°C venting at Marker A area, seeing many male and female octopus locomoting around this northern end of the outcrop, collecting a 50+ year old soda can for a microbiome analysis, and collecting a piece of wood with xyloplax echinoderms (fifth time ever observed!).** We deployed a new temperature logger and microbial trap experiments at Marker A, and collected one successful squeezer sample of fluid there. Near the end of the ascent we also witnessed a gulper eel with a full tummy!

Notable events:

Date & Time	Event	Image
2023-06-19 12:56	First view of Marker A after 9+ years - very little change	
2023-06-19 13:19	Squeezer sample at Marker A - max temp 11.3°C	
2023-06-19 13:47	Deployment of T logger 768602 and Microbe Traps at Marker A for recovery in December (note: some repositioning later in the dive)	
2023-06-19 14:07	Octopus collected near Marker A (venting fluid underneath 10.8°C, by eggs before collection 8.94°C), 10+ babies hatched during this process, plus a few sampled	

2023-06-19 15:59	Xyloplax on piece of wood	
2023-06-19 17:17	ROV in eye of octopus	
2023-06-19 18:10	50+ year old soda can, collected for microbiome analysis	

Fkt230602 Cruise Report

<p>2023-06-19 20:34</p>	<p>View of Marker B with basket stars</p>	An underwater photograph showing a greenish seabed. A yellow marker with the number '3' is visible in the center. Several basket stars are scattered across the seabed, and a small blue object is visible in the upper left.
<p>2023-06-19 21:00</p>	<p>Example of octopus on the move - many seen on this dive</p>	An underwater photograph of a pink octopus resting on a greenish seabed. The octopus is positioned in the center, with its tentacles curled. The seabed is covered in green algae and small rocks.
<p>2023-06-20 01:29</p>	<p>Gulper eel with full tummy</p>	An underwater photograph of a gulper eel swimming in the dark. The eel is positioned horizontally, with its head to the left and tail to the right. Its body is dark, and its large, inflated stomach is visible.

Daily plans

Wednesday 31 May 2023

- 8:00: Science party be ready to depart hotel
- 10:30: Science party arrival at water taxi
- 11:00: science party at vessel
- 13:00: Science party orientation

Thursday 1 June 2023

- 8:30: Team sediment planning meeting
- 9:30: Team Biology planning meeting in Conference Room
- 13:00: Boat drill
- 14:00: Dive planning meeting in Main Lab
- 16:00: Data overview training
- 17:00: Welcome BBQ @ outdoor lounge
- 19:00: Water sampling meeting in Conference Room
- 20:00: Departure - *make sure everything is secure before!!*
 - We will transit ~62.3 nmi @ 8 kn to a site over the trench to do first CTD cast
 - TARGET COORDINATES: 9.1262 / -85.2879

Friday 2 June 2023

- 4:00: Launch CTD #1 over trench (~3586 m water depth)
 - TARGET COORDINATES: 9.1262 / -85.2879
- **~8:15: Recover CTD #1**
 - Resume transit to Dorado Outcrop, ~100 nmi @ 8 kn
 - TARGET COORDINATES: 9.0840 / -87.0920
 - *Put off track by long line fishing in area*
- ~~8:30: Team Sediment meeting in Conference Room~~
- 9:30 Team animal meeting in Conference Room
- 10:00: Science at sea presentation for crew in mess
- 13:00: ROV/Control Room overview training in Hanger
- 16:00: Science meeting in Main Lab
- **21:30: On site over Dorado Outcrop, short narrow multibeam run**
 - ~~Start: 9.0805 / -87.0917~~
 - ~~End: 9.0917 / -87.1056~~
- **22:00: Launch CTD #2 over Dorado Outcrop for bottom water (~3000m water depth)**
 - COORDINATES: 9.08248 / -87.09545
- 23:20: Ship-to-shore with Bishop Museum (Beth + Diva)

Saturday 3 June 2023

- 01:30: Recovery CTD #2
 - First water samples!

Fkt230602 Cruise Report

- 02:00: Launch ROV for first dive at Dorado Outcrop (~3150m water depth)
 - LAUNCH COORDINATES: 9.07972 / -87.09722
- 17:00 - Science party meeting in Main Lab
- 19:00- Recover ROV Dive 529
- ~20:00 - Launch CTD #3 over "CTD-HydroMidN"
 - COORDINATES: 9.093527 / -87.022072
- ~23:30 - Recovery CTD #3

Sunday 4 June 2023

- ~03:00 - Launch ROV Dive 530 over Dorado Outcrop
 - COORDINATES: 9.0874 / -87.0983
- 10:30 weekly cabin checks
- ~21:00 - Science Party Meeting in the Main Lab
- ~23:00 - Recover ROV Dive 530; Begin transit to next site (~22 nmi)
 - COORDINATES: 8.7407 / -87.2085

Monday 5 June 2023

- 02:00 - Short multibeam lines (~10 nmi total) over small outcrop SW of Fuente @ 4 kt
 - Line 1: Start: 8.72845 / -87.20449; End: 8.75092 / -87.22600
 - Line 2: Start: 8.75406 / -87.22246; End: 8.72968 / -87.19917
 - Line 3: Start: 8.72328 / -87.20680; End: 8.74766 / -87.22955
 - *NOTE: this activity ended early*
- 05:00 - Deploy CTD #4 over outcrop SW of Fuente
 - COORDINATES: 8.740679 / -87.208489
- 08:00 - Recover CTD #4
- 10:00 - Launch ROV Dive 531 over small outcrop SW of Fuente
 - COORDINATES: 8.7503 / -87.2008
- 17:00 - Science Party meeting in Main Lab

Tuesday 6 June 2023

- 10:00 - Ship to Shore
- 11:00 - Recover ROV Dive 531
- 11:30 - Transit to Fuente Seamount
- 12:00 - begin multibeam over SW end of Fuente Seamount
- 19:00 - Launch of ROV Dive 532 at Fuente Seamount (~32 hours)
- 19:00 - Science party meeting in Main Lab

Wednesday 7 June 2023

- *ROV Dive Operations continue throughout the day*
- 06:00 - *World Ocean Day (June 8) begins western Pacific*
- 10:00 - Ship to Shore with Dolphins Academy (in Spanish: Carlos, Celeste, Sergio)

Thursday 8 June 2023

- 06:00 - recovery of ROV Dive 532

Fkt230602 Cruise Report

- ~~06:30~~ - ~~Begin transit to Puntarenas for mid-cruise event~~ - ~~160 nmi @ 7 kt~~
- 10:30 - *decision to cancel mid-cruise event, return to site*
- 11:00 - Ship to shore with Field Museum (Janet and Holly)
- 16:00 - on site over unnamed outcrop #2 SW of Fuente, begin multibeam mapping
 - Start Coordinates: 8.59575 / -87.30701

Line 1 Start	8.595749058	-87.30700558
Line 1 End	8.588284945	-87.32944176
Line 2 Start	8.595932677	-87.33485121
Line 2 End	8.623705649	-87.25860654
Line 3 Start	8.630941891	-87.26235226
Line 3 End	8.603581423	-87.33901405
Line 4 Start	8.610399848	-87.34650126
Line 4 End	8.639208852	-87.27087887
Line 5 Start	8.646651032	-87.27566428
Line 5 End	8.613283121	-87.35980378
Line 6 Start	8.621758449	-87.36438373
Line 6 End	8.634608755	-87.33426177

- 16:00 - Science party meeting

Friday 9 June 2023

- ~~09:00~~ - ~~Arrival in Puntarenas for mid-cruise event~~
- ~~10:30~~ - ~~VIP Tour Group arrives~~
- ~~12:00~~ - ~~VIP tour group departs~~
- ~~13:00~~ - ~~Academic tour group arrives~~
- ~~14:00~~ - ~~Academic tour group departs~~
- ~~14:30~~ - ~~Underway~~
- ~~16:00~~ - ~~Science party meeting~~
- 00:00 - End multibeam mapping, transit to Tengosed
 - Coordinates: 9.1188 / -86.9310
- 05:00 - Launch ROV dive S0533 at Tengosed Seamount
- 16:00 - Science party meeting in Main Lab
- 17:00 - Recover ROV Dive S0533, transit to CTD#5 HydroN station
 - Coordinates: 9.2406 / -86.9962, max depth 3195 m
- 19:00 - Launch CTD #5 - HydroN
- 23:00 - Recover CTD #5

Saturday 10 June 2023

- 05:00 - Launch ROV Dive S0534 at Tengosed seamount
 - COORDINATES: 9.11760 / -86.94611, max depth: 2,065 m
- 12:00 - Ship to shore with students from Texas (In English and Spanish; Gus, Sergio)
- 16:00 - Science party meeting in Main Lab
- 17:00 - Recover ROV
- 18:00 - Transit to area for multibeam mapping

Sunday 11 June 2023 - halfway point of cruise!

- 05:00 - Launch ROV Dive S0535 at unnamed feature near "Caballito"
 - Coordinates: 8.6265 / -87.2814

Fkt230602 Cruise Report

- 10:30 - Cabin Inspections
- 10:30 - Engine Room tour, group 1
- 13:30 - Engine Room tour, group 2
- 16:00 - Science party meeting in Main Lab
- 17:00 - Recover ROV, Transit to CTD # 6 location - "HydroSW":
 - Coordinates: 8.8125, -87.3238, max depth 3174 m
- 19:00 - Launch CTD #6
- 22:00 - Recover CTD #6, transit to CTD #7 location - near "Caballito"
 - Coordinates: 8.6202 / -87.3066, max depth 3142 m

Monday 12 June 2023

- 00:00 - Launch CTD #7
- 03:00 - Recover CTD #7, Transit to Dive 536 launch point
 - COORDINATES: 8.6143 / -87.2802, max depth 2980
- 05:00 - Launch ROV Dive 536 @ unnamed outcrop near Caballito
- 9:30 - Ship to shore with Explore by the Seat of Your Pants (English; Rachel & Gus)
- 13:30 - Science party meeting
- 15:30 - Recover ROV Dive 536
- 16:00 - Begin transit back to Puntarenas for medical evacuation (~20 hours)
 - Put off course by US naval vessels along path
- ~~- 16:00 - Science party meeting in Main lab~~
- ~~- 17:00 - Recover ROV Dive 536~~

Tuesday 13 June 2023

- 10:00 - Science party group photo
- 10:30 - arrival at station in port for personnel transfer
- 11:30 - begin transit back to site (~22.5 hours)
- 16:00 - Science party meeting in Conference Room

Wednesday 14 June 2023

- 09:00 - arrive on station and Launch ROV Dive 537 @ Dorado Outcrop
 - COORDINATES: 9.0825 / -87.0954, max depth 3,000 m
- 10:00 - Ship to Shore with UNED (in Spanish)
- 14:00 - Hot wing contest in Mess
- 19:00 - Science party meeting in Main Lab
- 21:00 - Recover ROV Dive 537, transit to CTD #8 location "HydroCenter"
 - COORDINATES: 8.9859 / -87.1026, max depth 3,200 m

Thursday 15 June 2023

- ~~05:00~~ - Launch ROV Dive 538 @ unnamed E of Caballito
 - Coordinates: 8.6217, -87.2796. max depth 3073
 - *Delayed to 05:30 due to needing to divert around long line fishing in the area*
- 19:00 - Science party meeting

Fkt230602 Cruise Report

- 21:00 - Recover ROV Dive 538, proceed to MB around Caballito

Line 1 Start	8.65740168	-87.28039867
Line 1 End	8.63870084	-87.32810081
Line 2 Start	8.631200503	-87.36820261
Line 2 End	8.665102026	-87.28599892
Line 3 Start	8.672702367	-87.29099915
Line 3 End	8.64070093	-87.37110274

- Multibeam track ended up being different than these lines because of fishing boat in the area

Friday 16 June 2023

- 05:00 - Launch ROV Dive 539 @ Caballito
 - COORDINATES: 8.6174 / -87.3141, max depth 3142
- 10:00 - Ship to Shore with UNED (in Spanish)
- 16:00 - Science party geology meeting in Conference Room
- 19:00 - Science party meeting in Main Lab
- 21:00 - Recovery ROV Dive 539
- 22:00 - Multibeam southwest of Caballito

Line 1 Start	8.5165	-87.3123
Line 1 End	8.5822	-87.3774
Line 2 Start	8.5880	-87.3693
Line 2 End	8.5359	-87.3211
Line 3 Start	8.5463	-87.3213
Line 3 End	8.5925	-87.3604

- ~~22:15 - Movie night "Life Aquatic"~~

Saturday 17 June 2023

- 05:00 - Launch ROV Dive 540 @ Caballito
 - COORDINATES: 8.6361 / -87.3327, max depth: 3183
- 12:30 - *Optional* science party tutorial on "how to make a dive plan" in Main Lab
- 16:00 - Science party geology meeting in Conference Room
- 19:00 - Science party meeting in Main Lab
- 21:00 - Recover ROV Dive 540, transit to CTD #9 HydroMidS station
 - COORDINATES: 8.9038 / -87.1768, max depth: 3210
- 22:00 - Launch CTD #9 HydroMidS station

Sunday 18 June 2023

- 00:00 - Launch CTD #9 HydroMidS station
- 02:30 - Recover CTD#9, transit to ROV Dive 541 site
- 05:00 - ROV Dive 541 @ Tengosed

Fkt230602 Cruise Report

- Coordinates: 9.11303 / -86.94234, max depth: 2131 m
- 10:30 - Cabin Inspections!
- 19:00 - Science party meeting in Main Lab
- 21:00 - Recover ROV Dive 541
- 22:00 - Launch CTD #10 at Tengosed
 - Coordinates: 9.132697 / -86.942171, max depth: 2000m

Monday 19 June 2023

- 01:00 - Recover CTD#10, Transit to Dorado
 - Coordinates: 9.08872 / -87.10170
- 04:00 - Launch ROV Dive 542 @ Dorado (including hull inspection)
- 10:00 - Ship to Shore with UNED (in Spanish)
- 21:00 - Recover ROV Dive 542, transit to CTD #11 location (~6 nmi)
- 23:00 - Launch CTD #11 HydroMidW station
 - COORDINATES: 9.0201 / -87.1612, max depth 3,165

Tuesday 20 June 2023

- 02:00 - Recover CTD #11, transit to CTD #12 location (~8 nmi)
- 03:30 - Launch CTD #12 HydroMidE station - **LAST CTD AT SITE**
 - COORDINATES: 8.9463 / -87.0407, max depth 3184 m
- 06:30 - Recover CTD #12, transit to CTD#13 location (~84 nmi = ~10 hrs)
- 08:00 - co-chief interview with Science/AAAS
- 08:30 - Group photo
- 09:00 - Ship to Shore with Colegio Metropolitano (In Spanish, Carlos)
- 10:30 - Tator tutorial in Conference Room
- 13:00 - [boat drill - not for science party]
- 15:00 - co-chief debrief with SOI
- 15:30 - Launch CTD #13 Trench2 station - LAST CTD
 - COORDINATES: 9.1721 / -85.6434, max depth 3,734 m
- **17:00 - ALL TABLES/PHOTOS/ETC. REPORTS DUE IN PARTICIPANT DATA FOLDER FOR COPYING TO CRUISE HARD DRIVE, CRUISE REPORT SECTION in GDRIVE**
- 17:30 - BBQ
- 19:00 - Recover CTD #13, transit to port (~84 nmi = ~10 hours)
- 19:30 - movie night

Wednesday 21 June 2023

- 08:00 - Arrival at anchorage in Puntarenas, pick up passports in mess
- 10:30 - VIP Tour Group arrives
- 12:00 - VIP tour group departs
- 13:00 - Academic tour group arrives
- 14:30 - Academic tour group departs
- 16:00 - Science party meeting in mess
- 17:00 - Disembark via water taxi for post-cruise dinner in Puntarenas

Fkt230602 Cruise Report

- 20:30 - Return to dock for water taxi back to ship

Thursday 22 June 2023

- 9:00 - Dry-ice arrives, Group 2 packs samples, Group 1 Disembark with gear
- 10:00 - Group 2 disembarks with samples
- 11:00 - final loading at the dock and depart
- 13:00 - lunch stop
- 14:30 - final ~30 min journey to hotel, UCR team to UCR

Biology/Animal Specimen Summary

Samples

ROV SuBastian collected a total of 150 primary biological samples for taxonomic identification and ground truthing of identifications from images. A large number and diversity of biological associates were also collected. The highest number of samples were collected from Dorado Outcrop, followed by the unnamed outcrop East of Caballito. Echinoderms were the most collected taxonomic group (n=39), followed by octocorals (n=37), molluscs (n=27, including 25 cephalopods) and sponges (n=25), and crustaceans (n=22; Table 6). Further identification of collected specimens will be led by scientists from Universidad de Costa Rica in collaboration with international experts on morphological taxonomy.

Table 6. Taxonomic groupings of primary biological specimens collected (not including associates).

Taxonomic ID	Caballito	Dorado Outcrop	Fuente Seamount	Tengosed Seamount	Unnamed outcrop E of Caballito	Unnamed outcrop SW of Fuente	Total
Octocorallia	5	13	4	9	4	2	37
<i>Anthomastus</i> sp.	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
<i>Candidella</i> cf. <i>gigantea</i>	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
<i>Candidella</i> sp.	0	0	1	0	0	1	2
<i>Chrysogorgiidae</i> sp.?	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
<i>Halipteris</i> sp.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Keratoisis</i> sp.	0	1	1	0	0	0	2
<i>Isididae</i> sp.	0	3	1	0	0	0	4
<i>Paragorgia</i> sp.	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
<i>Primnoidae</i> sp.	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
<i>Swiftia</i> sp.	0	0	0	3	0	0	3
<i>Umbellula</i> sp.?	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
<i>Unknown</i>	4	8	2	6	3	2	25
Antipatharia	0	1	0	4	1	0	6
<i>Bathypathes</i> cf. <i>alternata</i> ?	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
<i>Heteropathes</i> cf. <i>americana</i> ?	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
<i>Aphanipathes</i> sp.?	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
<i>Unknown</i>	0	0	0	2	1	0	3
Bryozoa	1	1	0	0	0	0	2
<i>Unknown</i>	1	1	0	0	0	0	2
Crustacea	3	13	0	0	6	0	22
<i>Lebbeus</i> cf. <i>scrippsi</i>	0	1	0	0	0	0	1

Fkt230602 Cruise Report

<i>Alvinocaris costaricensis</i>	0	6	0	0	2	0	8
<i>Lebbeus scrippsi?</i>	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
<i>Nematocarcinus</i> sp.	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
<i>Paguridae</i> sp.? <i>Zoantharia?</i>	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
<i>Spongicoloides</i> sp.?	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
Unknown	0	2	0	0	3	0	5
Echinodermata	6	5	0	11	8	9	39
<i>Amperima/Peniagone</i> sp.?	2	0	0	0	1	0	3
<i>Crinoidea</i> sp.?	1	1	0	0	0	0	2
<i>Pannychia</i> sp.	0	0	0	3	0	0	3
<i>Psychropotidae</i> sp.	3	0	0	0	0	0	3
Unknown	0	4	0	8	7	9	28
Hydrozoa	1	2	0	0	1	0	4
Unknown	1	2	0	0	1	0	4
Mollusca	3	12	1	2	7	2	27
<i>Amphitretidae</i> sp.	1	0	0	0	3	0	4
<i>Graneledone</i> sp.	0	0	0	0	0	2	2
<i>Muusoctopus</i> sp.	1	12	1	2	3	0	19
<i>Velutinidae</i> sp.	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
Unknown	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
Porifera	6	11	1	7	0	0	25
<i>Euplectella?</i> sp.	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
Unknown	3	7	0	4	0	0	14
Scleractinia	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
Unknown	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
Annelida	6	3	1	0	1	0	11
<i>Terebellidae</i> sp.	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
Unknown	5	3	1	0	1	0	10
Other	3	3	1	3	0	0	10
Total	28	60	9	27	20	6	150

Transects and video annotation

Thirty-one video transects were conducted at four sites with the ROV video/still imaging systems: 11 at Dorado Outcrop, 7 at unnamed outcrop SW of Fuente, 3 at unnamed outcrop E of Caballito, and 10 at Caballito (Table 7). The majority of these surveys were conducted in the sedimented abyssal plain (n=22), with only 9 collected on the outcrops. This was an operational outcome of primarily conducted transects between heat flow measurement sites. The transects varied between 50 and 100 meters in length. For the majority, transects were completed at

0.1-0.2 meters per second, 1 meter above bottom, with 10-cm lasers on, and the science camera set to no zoom and tilted just above the ROV tool tray.

Table 7. List of video transects from Fkt230602

Dive	Location	# of transects (abyssal / outcrop)	Notes
529	Dorado	3 (1/2)	Likely not usable due to poor parameters
530	Dorado	8 (5/3)	
531	Unnamed outcrop SW Fuente	7 (7/0)	
538	Unnamed outcrop E Caballito	3 (0/3)	
539	Caballito	4 (4/0)	
540	Caballito	6 (5/1)	

Analyses of these surveys should provide data on megafaunal abundance, diversity, and community structure, including with substrate variation locally and regionally; though the results will likely be skewed towards sedimented abyssal plain areas. Analyses of these ROV video/still surveys will be led by scientists from Universidad de Costa Rica in collaboration with international experts, using state-of-the-art image analyses and statistical approaches.

The Fkt230602 expedition was the first for RV *Falkor (too)* to incorporate use of the Tator (www.tator.io) video annotation platform for annotating biological and geological observations in near-real time both shipboard and with shore-based collaborators. Tator is a web platform for analyzing large video and image datasets, allowing the annotation of footage, which involves labeling or marking specific objects, events, or attributes within a video dataset. Video annotation is used in research, computer vision, and machine learning to train and evaluate algorithms. Video annotation holds great potential for deep sea analysis, where understanding the behaviors and interactions of marine organisms in their natural habitat is crucial. By annotating our deep-sea video footage, we will gain valuable insights into the behavior, distribution, and ecology of organisms that reside in this unique and often inaccessible environment. Some specific applications of video annotation in deep-sea analysis include species identification, behavioral analysis, habitat mapping, and environmental monitoring. Since Tator developers and SOI data architects were able to upload videos near real-time to the Tator cloud, we also were able to have a shore-based team who followed the expedition and helped with annotations. Two shore-based people were actively making annotations on SuBastian's video footage. Table 8 summarize the estimated time of video footage (~207 hours) that we started to analyze and that needs to be finished after the expedition.

During the Octopus Odyssey expedition, we maintained effective communication to address project inconsistencies, including missing video files (from SuBastian's descents and ascents) and the need for additional annotation fields. A training session on board for the science party

sparked insightful discussions about Tator's potential for our work and future expeditions. We compiled recommendations for improvements and will plan to have a virtual meeting with SOI and Tator personnel to share our experience and potential improvements.

It is important to note that post-expedition validation and refinement are necessary for accurate identification due to the complexity and novelty of deep-sea ecosystems. Collaboration with taxonomists and the Tator platform is crucial for precise annotations. This validation process will ensure the scientific rigor and reliability of the findings.

Some useful links to work on Tator include:

- **Introduction to Tator:** [Explanation](#) by Benjamin Woodward (FathomNet Workshop 2023)
- **Tator Demo:** [10 min video demo](#).
- **Tator official documentation:**
 - <https://www.tator.io/docs>
 - Annotation: <https://www.tator.io/docs/user-guide/annotation>
 - Draw localizations (tutorial): <https://youtu.be/RZGjWK42308>

Table 8. Summary of video files and estimated time lengths from ROV SuBastian dives available on Tator Cloud

Dive number	Number of video files	Hours of video
0529	27	11.7
0530	34	14.7
0531	46	22.3
0532	66	31.1
0533	27	10.0
0534	24	10.8
0535	23	10.5
0536	28	10.3
0537	25	11.6
0538	33	15.6
0539	38	15.5
0540	46	12.5
0541	32	15.2
0542	34	16.1
Total	483	207.9

Figure 3. Example of localization drawing on Tator platform

Octopus specimen collection and microbiome sampling

Methods: Specimens were collected using ROV manipulators and assorted tools (manipulator grab, hand net, metal scoop for benthic species; suction sampler for mid-water species) and placed into bioboxes or suction sampler containers. Some octopus were brooding or associated with previously deployed equipment (plastic crates) and were opportunistically collected; some animals were exposed to ambient water throughout ROV ascent. Upon ROV recovery, animals were transferred from their storage locations to plastic containers filled with uncontaminated chilled sea water. If still alive when reaching the surface, animals were narcotized with 3% ethanol diluted with sea water. Full narcotization was achieved when the animal failed to show righting reflex and respiration. All animals were photographed, with special attention paid to hectocotylus in males. Muscle was then collected in 95% ethanol for molecular analyses, and

some individuals were then subjected to additional microbiome sampling. Specimen vouchers of benthic species (*Muusoctopus* spp., *Graneledone* sp.) were preserved in 10 % formalin, and midwater species (*Amphitretidae*) were preserved in 95% ethanol, and taxonomy preliminarily assigned. Eggs from brooding females were also collected. Subsamples of egg casings and juveniles or hatchlings were preserved in 95% ethanol, Zymo, and 2% paraformaldehyde. Except for individuals preserved as fully intact vouchers, octopus were dissected fresh and sampled at multiple anatomical sites for investigation of associated microbiota. Sampling included: skin, gills, renal appendage, esophagus, posterior salivary gland, crop, stomach, and gonads (distal and posterior oviduct in females, spermatophore in males). Dissected samples were taken in duplicate and preserved in 1) Zymo DNA/RNA shield for molecular analyses and 2) 2% paraformaldehyde for histology and fluorescence *in situ* hybridization. Muscle tissue was taken from every individual and preserved in 95% ethanol for molecular analyses.

Sample summary: A total of 25 cephalopod specimens of adult octopus (4x males and 10x females), octopus egg clutches (7), and mid-water octopus (4) were collected on ten of the 14 ROV dives, and from all of the six locations visited on the expedition (Table 9). Of these, the majority were of the *Muusoctopus* sp. (n=19), with a few *Graneledone* sp. (n=2) and four mid-water species (n=4). Of these 25 specimens, 13 were subsampled for microbiomes: 2 *Muusoctopus* males, 5 *Muusoctopus* females, 5 *Muusoctopus* egg clutches, and one mid-water species. No microbiome samples were collected from *Graneledone* specimens as both were retained as voucher specimens.

Table 9. Summary of cephalopod samples collected on the expedition.

Asterisks indicate potential type specimens.

Dive	Site name	Sample ID	SpeciesID	Sex	Microbiome Sampling
529	Dorado Outcrop	014*	<i>Muusoctopus</i> sp. 1	Male	No
529	Dorado Outcrop	015*	<i>Muusoctopus</i> sp. 1	Female	No
529	Dorado Outcrop	016	<i>Muusoctopus</i> sp. 1	Eggs	Yes
529	Dorado Outcrop	017	<i>Muusoctopus</i> sp. 1	Eggs/Hatchlings	Yes
529	Dorado Outcrop	018	<i>Muusoctopus</i> sp. 1	Eggs	Yes
530	Dorado Outcrop	041	<i>Muusoctopus</i> sp. 1	Female	Yes
530	Dorado Outcrop	042	<i>Muusoctopus</i> sp. 1	Female	Yes
530	Dorado Outcrop	043	<i>Muusoctopus</i> sp. 1	Female	Yes
530	Dorado Outcrop	056	<i>Muusoctopus</i> sp. 1	Male	No
531	OC SW of Fuente	067*	<i>Graneledone</i> sp.	Female	No
531	OC SW of Fuente	068*	<i>Graneledone</i> sp.	Eggs	No

532	Fuente Seamount	096	Muusoctopus sp. 1	Female	Yes
536	OC E of Caballito	160	Muusoctopus sp. 1	Egg casing	Yes
536	OC E of Caballito	161	Muusoctopus sp. 1	Female	Yes
536	OC E of Caballito	165*	Amphitretidae sp.	Female	No
537	Dorado Outcrop	180	Muusoctopus sp. 1	Male	Yes
538	OC E of Caballito	212*	Amphitretidae sp.	Unknown	No
538	OC E of Caballito	213	Amphitretidae sp.	Unknown	Yes
540	Caballito	244*	Muusoctopus sp. 2	Female	No
540	Caballito	245	Amphitretidae sp.	Female	No
541	Tengosed Seamount	267*	<i>Muusoctopus</i> sp. 3	Female	No
541	Tengosed Seamount	268	<i>Muusoctopus</i> sp. 3	Eggs that hatched	No
542	Dorado Outcrop	273	Muusoctopus sp. 1	Female	No
542	Dorado Outcrop	274	Muusoctopus sp. 1	Eggs/hatchlings	Yes

Key octopus findings (see Figure 4):

- Confirmation of viable octopus nurseries: *Muusoctopus* females brooding viable eggs at the previously discovered “octopus garden” at Dorado Outcrop, as well as at a newly discovered site on the unnamed outcrop E of Caballito. In addition to observing embryos at various stages of development, we were able to document real-time hatching of juvenile octopus. During targeted collection of individual brooding female *Muusoctopus*, the disruption of brooding allowed observation of rapid predation by shrimp and eels, underscoring the importance of maternal attendance to eggs
- Temporal variability in octopus: Much higher density of octopus at Dorado Outcrop since 2014. While the new nursery discovered at the unnamed outcrop E of Caballito did not have the same density of brooding octopus as Dorado Outcrop, we observed several rocks with egg cement, indicating that those places previously had egg cases.
- Sexual size dimorphism: Males at Dorado are significantly larger than females brooding in warmer fluids, though one single female collected away from warm fluid was as large as the males. This is basically unknown amongst cephalopods.
- *Muusoctopus* and *Graneledone* species and specimen variability:
 - Dorado *Muusoctopus* sp. 1 female octopods are very similar in appearance to one individual collected near Davidson Seamount (housed at Field Museum) but may exhibit some subtle differences in arm morphology and skin texture.
 - A single *Muusoctopus* female collected from Fuente had slightly different morphology from those observed at Dorado Outcrop: shorter mantle, longer arms, fewer gill lamellae.

- The Muusoctopus specimen (referred to as species 2, Fkt230602_244) from Caballito (no venting) had longer arms, less crowded suckers, and a narrower head than the species from Dorado Outcrop and unnamed outcrop E of Caballito.
- A third Muusoctopus species collected from Tengosed seamount had remnants of reverse countershading, long arms, and pronounced constriction between head and eyes. This specimen was nearly senescent on the seafloor, and hatchlings were observed and collected.
- The Graneledone sp. collected from the unnamed outcrop SW of Fuente may be a new species, most similar to one discussed but not named from central Chile.
- One of the mid-water octopus collected had a prominent bioluminescent organ at the base of the arms surrounding the buccal opening. This feature has been described in maturing amphitretid females and is thought to play a role in reproductive signaling.

Figure 4. Photographs of cephalopod specimens

Figure 4A. View of male Muusoctopus from Dorado Outcrop (Fkt230602_014)

Figure 4B. view of female Muusoctopus from Dorado Outcrop (Fkt230602_015)

Figure 4C. View of Muusoctopus eggs and hatchlings from Dorado Outcrop (Fkt230602_017)

Figure 4D. Another view of Muusoctopus hatchlings from Dorado Outcrop (Fkt230602_017)

Figure 4E. Ventral view of female *Graneledone* sp. (samples Fkt230602_067) collected from unnamed outcrop SW of Fuente that may be a new species.

Figure 4F. In situ photograph of female *Muusoctopus* specimen Fkt230602_069 from Fuente Seamount.

Figure 4G. Frontal view in situ of Amphitretid mid-water octopus Fkt230602_165

Figure 4H. Bioluminescent organ (yellow ring) seen at the based of arms in specimen Fkt230602_165.

Figure 4I. Closeup view of hectocotylus on male *Muusoctopus* Fkt230602_180

Figure 4J. *Muusoctopus* sp. 2. Female adult (Fkt230602_244)

Figure 4K. *Muusoctopus* sp. 3 from Tenosed Seamount (Fkt230602_267)

Figure 4L. Hatchlings from eggs collected from Fkt230602_267 female, sampled for microbiome (Fkt230602_268)

Figure 4M. Closeup view of hectocotylus on male *Muusoctopus* Fkt230602_180

Figure 4N. *Muusoctopus* sp. 2. Female adult (Fkt230602_244)

Figure 4P. Muusoctopus sp. 3 from Tenosed Seamount (Fkt230602_267)

Figure 4Q. Hatchlings from eggs collected from Fkt230602_267 female, sampled for microbiome (Fkt230602_268)

Rock Sample summary

Thirty (30) rock sample types were collected during the expedition, ranging from basalts, indurated and lithified sediments, nodules, and an encrusted beaked whale rostrum (Tables 10, 11). Nine of these were subsampled for microbiological analysis (method described below). The majority of the dry rock samples will be sent to the USGS for characterization of the mineral crusts on the exteriors of the samples. Select subsamples and reference samples, including the beaked whale rostrum, will be archived by the Department of Geology at UCR.

Methods for rock subsampling for microbiological analysis: Two-gallon buckets and lids were surface sterilized with ethanol by spraying 70% ethanol from a spray bottle and wiping with a paper towel. These buckets were then filled with sea water that had been filtered through 0.2 micron filters from previous dives. Buckets were then left in the cold room at $\sim 4^{\circ}\text{C}$. Rocks collected for microbiology were removed while wearing gloves from the rock boxes on the ROV and placed into the bucket with cold sterile seawater for movement around the ship. Some rocks were left in these buckets in the cold room overnight and processed the next morning. For processing, rocks were placed in the stainless steel “rock box”, which had been previously ethanol-sterilized by spraying 70% ethanol on the surfaces and allowing the ethanol to evaporate over several hours. Prior to subsampling, pictures were taken of the intact rock. The piece of rock for microbiological subsampling was broken off using a hammer and autoclaved chisel. The larger portion of rock intended for geological study was removed and allowed to air dry in a plastic tub on the lab bench. The microbiology subsample was broken into small chunks using the autoclaved chisel. These chunks were then placed in an autoclaved mortar and ground to smaller pieces using an autoclaved pestle. Chunks of rock intended for DNA extraction were placed in a 50 ml Falcon tube ($\sim 30\text{-}40$ cc) using autoclaved scoops and tweezers and immediately placed in the -80°C freezer. Rock homogenate for organic carbon analysis ($\sim 2\text{-}5$ cc) was placed in 20 ml glass vials using sterile scoops and placed in the -30°C freezer. Subsamples of homogenate for microbial cell counts were placed in duplicate 2ml microcentrifuge tubes that had previously been filled with cold 0.2 micron filtered formaldehyde diluted in PBS that had been stored in the 4°C refrigerator. Extra homogenate for geological analysis by the USGS was placed in 15 ml Falcon tubes and stored at room temperature.

Table 10. Rock Samples Descriptions (by Beth Orcutt)

Site	Dive	# of rock samples (description - BOLD = MBIO samples)
Dorado Outcrop	529	- 012 nodules - 018 crusted mudstone with octo egg casings - 019 basalt pillow w> worm tubes
Dorado Outcrop	530	- 030 nodule w/ coral - 045 groundmass with thin crust veneer - 046 indurated sediment (2) with iron oxide staining + worms
Unnamed SW Fuente	531	- 061 carbonate siliceous ooze
Fuente	532	- 080 indurated mudstone w/ thin veneer black Mn oxides, holes - 082 mudstone/shale w/ thin veneer of black crumbly material - 083 soft crumbly calcareous ooze, hole in places - 094 black crumbly texture
Tengosed	533	- 110 altered groundmass, 2-4mm black crust, iron oxides, egg cases attached - 123 sediment breccia with 2-4mm thick black rind on top, some iron oxide staining
Tengosed	534	- 130 laminated mudstone w/ worm tubes with mm-cm black crust - 131 carbonate ooze (not archived) - 139 mildly botryoidal crust, dark grey to black, had bio attached
Unnamed E Caballito	535	- 156 small piece, difficult to determine origin
Unnamed E Caballito	536	- 160 indurated laminated dark chocolate brown sediment w/ thin smooth veneer - 164 siltstone with thin black veneer, coated in worm tubes
Unnamed E Caballito	538	- 189 very crumbly & friable mudstone w/ black crumbly crust, coated in worms
Caballito	539	- 225 encrusted beak whale rostrum - 227 nodule from sediment field - 228 carbonate ooze
Caballito	540	- 249 pillow basalt, sparsely phyrlic, no glass - 250 pillow basalt, sparsely phyrlic, no glass

Tengosed	541	- 260 carbonate ooze - 261 ledge over ooze piece. Hard black crust. Worms on top - 270 dark grey siltstone w/ <1cm black crumbly crust - 271 dark grey siltstone w/ 2-4mm black crumbly crust
Dorado	542	- 278 botryoidal nodule

Table 11. Smear slides from sediments inside rock samples (by Maria Isabel Sandoval)

Location	Sample #	Description	Photo
Unnamed outcrop SW of Fuente Seamount	Rock sample 067	Calcareous siliceous ooze with planktonic foraminifera, coccolithophores and radiolarians (<i>Cyrtocapsella cornuta</i> , <i>Didymocyrtis laticonus</i> , <i>Spongurus</i> spp.) The radiolarian assemblage is from late Miocene.	<p><i>Didymocyrtis laticonus</i></p>
Unnamed outcrop SW of Fuente Seamount	Rock sample 067	Calcareous siliceous ooze with planktonic foraminifera, coccolithophores and radiolarians (<i>Cyrtocapsella cornuta</i> , <i>Didymocyrtis laticonus</i> , <i>Spongurus</i> spp.) The radiolarian assemblage is from late Miocene.	<p><i>Didymocyrtis laticonus</i></p>
Fuente Seamount	Rock sample 080	Calcareous siliceous ooze with foraminifera, coccolithophores and sponge spicules.	<p>Calcareous nannoplankton</p>

Fkt230602 Cruise Report

Fuente Seamount	Rock sample 082	Siltstone with plagioclase and mud fragments, Fe oxides, few sponge spicules.	<p>Siltstone</p>
Fuente Seamount	Rock sample 083	Mudstone/grainstone with foraminifera and coccolithophores. No siliceous fraction is observed.	<p>Foraminifers' fragments</p>
Tengosed Seamount	Rock sample 130	Altered basaltic lava with some laminated siltstone filling within fractures. Smear slide of the laminated siltstone is composed of acicular mineral like apatite?, and calcareous nannoplankton.	<p>Apatite?</p>
Tengosed Seamount	Rock sample 131	Calcareous ooze with foraminifera and few diatoms.	<p>Foraminifers</p>
Caballito	Rock sample 228	Calcareous siliceous ooze with nannoplankton, planktonic foraminifera, radiolarians, diatoms and silicoflagellates. Radiolarians include: <i>Cyrtocapsella tetrapera</i> from late Miocene	<p><i>Cyrtocapsella tetrapera</i> (late Miocene)</p>

Fkt230602 Cruise Report

Tengosed Seamount	Rock sample 260	Calcareous siliceous ooze (grainstone), foraminifera, calcareous nannoplankton	<p>Benthic foraminifera</p>
Tengosed Seamount	Rock sample 261	Siltstone with mud fragments, minerals (pyroxenes, apatite?, plagioclases)	<p>Mud fragments</p>
Tengosed Seamount	Rock sample 270	Siltstone with mud fragments and minerals	<p>Mud fragments</p>

Sediment Sample summary

Methods: The Subastian coring set up consists of push cores of 26cm H, and 7.25cm OD, and 6.75cm ID. The ROV is equipped with a fore portside sliding, 8 core, locked basket with bungee holders in each core holster. Each dive is equipped to carry a total of 8 sediment push cores, including 2 cores with taped 3mm diameter holes for ship-based geochemical sampling using rhizones. The original core basket design uses a bungee strap for each of the eight cores. The eight holsters carrying each push core are interconnected in an aluminum rack that must be removed, held in place by screws, as a single sliding unit from the ROV frame. The aluminum holster frame, containing all collected samples for each dive was placed in the “dirty” wet lab area of the ROV hanger, directly adjacent to the CTD launch bay. Each holster holds the plastic cores in place gravitationally, with preloaded plastic bottoms which prevent the sample from sliding out of the bottom of each core, with two snug 3cm pins at the holster bottom. These pins must have their handles facing outward for easy sliding. A two-worker team was necessary to remove the bottom holster pins and maintain the core in the holster, which is subsequently slid out from beneath. Once removed each sediment push core was transferred to 6.75cm diameter core extruder from which all sectioning was made. The sturdier was washed with a freshwater hose rinse following each core sampling. In the interest of saving valuable dive time, the science party originally suggested not to strap cores with bungees following sampling and holstering at the seafloor. This suggestion, was later recanted due to core loss events that the pilots attributed to sediment

“bubble/gas” release on ascend on a couple of occasions, as detailed below.

Samples: Nine of fourteen ROV Subastian dives during this cruise successfully sampled 66 sediment push cores from the flanks of all six seafloor features visited on the expedition (Table 12). These collections were subsampled into 183 independent samples for a wide variety of analyses, including description of sediment fungi and worms (by shore based collaborator Keiler Rojas, UCR), description of sediment protists and meiofauna, sediment physical description via

smear slides (by Maria Sandoval), description of sediment porewater geochemistry (by shore based collaborator Geoff Wheat) and microbial community taxonomic and functional diversity with 'omics based approaches (by Gustavo Ramírez) and assessment of sedimental microbial community ecotoxicology sensitivity to cadmium (by Miguel Semedo). Sediment sample smear slides of sediment revealed that sediments were siliceous clays of varying composition (Table 13).

Table 12. Overview of sediment push cores collected for various analyses, with sample numbers for various analyses.

Dive	Location	# cores	DNA/ Geochem	Fungi / Worms / Genetics	Plastic	Geol	Ecotox / Metal / Bact. Isolation
529	Dorado	8	4	9	6	5,7,8	2
530	Dorado	7	34	36	33	33, 35, 39, 40	37
531	Unnamed SW Fuente	7	76	79	79	73, 74, 77	78
532	Fuente	5	87	90	90	88, 90, 91	101
533	Tengosed	8	119	114	118	113, 115, 117, 118	120
535	Unnamed E of Caballito	8	158	152, 151	154	148, 149, 153	150
538	Unnamed E of Caballito	8	202	195	-	200, 202	201
539	Caballito	6	220	219	215	216, 218	-
540	Caballito	8	237	236	238	234, 239, 240	241

Table 13. Sediment smear slides.

Location	Sample #	Description	Photo
Dorado Outcrop	Push core sample 007 smear slides (0-1 cm), (2-3 cm) and (10-11 cm).	Siliceous clay with plagioclases, biotites, Fe oxides, diatoms (<i>Coscinodiscus</i>), radiolarian (<i>Stylodictya</i> sp, <i>Cornutella profunda</i> , <i>Amphirhopalum ypsilon</i>), foraminifera, silicoflagellates. Bad preservation in general.	<p><i>Coscinodiscus</i> sp. (0-1 cm)</p>

Fkt230602 Cruise Report

<p>Fuente Seamount</p>	<p>Push core sample 088, smear slides (4-5 cm) and (10-11 cm)</p>	<p>Siliceous clay with mud fragments, plagioclases, biotites, Fe oxides, diatoms (<i>Coscinodiscus</i>), pyroxenes, chlorite?.</p>	<p><i>Coscinodiscus</i> sp. (4-5 cm)</p>
<p>Tengosed Seamount</p>	<p>Push core sample 117, smear slides (0-1 cm) and (15-16 cm)</p>	<p>Siliceous clay with mud fragments, organic matter?, chlorite?, plagioclases, biotites, Fe oxides, foraminifers, diatoms and microscleres.</p>	<p>Fe oxides and mud fragments (0-1 cm)</p>
<p>Unnamed outcrop E Caballito</p>	<p>Push core sample 148, smear slides (1-2 cm), (6-7 cm) and (17-18)</p>	<p>1-2 cm: Siliceous clay with mud fragments, plagioclases (pyroxenes), few diatoms (<i>Coscinodiscus</i>), radiolarians, fragments, some few <i>Stylosphaera</i>, low Fe oxides. 6-7 cm: Siliceous clay with mud fragments, plagioclases, foraminifera, biotites, radiolarians. Radiolarians include: <i>P. corbula</i>, and <i>A. ypsilon</i>. and <i>Spongaster</i> sp. 17-18 cm: Siliceous clay with mud fragments, foraminifera, copepods?, plagioclases.</p>	<p><i>Phormostichoartus corbula</i> (6-7 cm)</p>
<p>Unnamed outcrop E of Caballito</p>	<p>Push core sample 200 smear slides (0-1), (9-10) and (17-18)</p>	<p>0-1: Siliceous clay with mud fragments, diatoms (Fe oxides), biotites, plagioclase, radiolarians such as <i>P. corbula</i> and <i>Stylodictya</i> sp., chlorite, carapace (amphipod?) 9-10 cm: Siliceous clay with mud fragments, few diatoms and altered radiolarians. 17-18 cm: Siliceous mud fragments, plagioclases, radiolarians (<i>B. aquilonaris</i>), pyroxene, foraminifera, biotite (<i>Spongocore puella</i>, <i>A. ypsilon</i>, <i>P. corbula</i>)</p>	<p>Carapace (amphipod?) (0-1 cm)</p>

Squeezer Sample summary

Thirteen fluid samples were collected from Dorado Outcrop and the unnamed outcrop E of Caballito with the third-party squeezers supplied by Geoff Wheat and assembled by Tim D'Angelo, using the following methods (Table 14).

Prior to each dive the squeezer samplers were subject to a cleaning process to make them as sterile and trace element free as possible. First, ~50 ml of distilled water was sucked in to the chamber and swished around for ~10 seconds and purged from the chamber, this process was done three times. Then ~20 ml of 70% ethanol was sucked in to the chamber and swished around for 10 seconds then purged from the chamber. The chamber was then washed with distilled water as described above. Next, ~50 ml of 10% hydrochloric acid was sucked in to the chamber and swished and ejected as described above, twice. Lastly, the chambers were cleaned with autoclaved MilliQ water as described above, twice. The final priming was performed with autoclaved MilliQ water.

The squeezers were immediately transferred to the 4°C cold room upon recovering from the ROV after the dive. The contents of the squeezers (~200 ml) were transferred to five sterile 50 ml Falcon tubes. Geochemical subsamples were taken unfiltered from the fluid for nutrients, major ions and acidified ions. These subsamples were placed in acid washed HDPE screw-top vials. The 8 ml nutrients subsample was immediately frozen. The 4 ml major ions sample was taken and stored in the 4°C refrigerator. The 4 ml acidified ions subsample had 32 µl of optima hydrochloric acid added to it and stored in the 4°C refrigerator.

For cell counts of microbial biomass, duplicate 600 µl subsamples of the fluid was pipetted into 1.5 ml cryovials that had been pre-filled with 600 µl of cold 0.2 micron filtered 37% formaldehyde and stored at 4°C prior to use. These samples were stored at 4°C. Duplicate 1000 µl subsamples for single cell genomics were pipetted into 1.5 ml cryovials. The samples were cryopreserved by addition 100 µl of 10x glyTE, mixed by several inversions and then flash frozen using liquid nitrogen. The remaining fluid (~180 ml) was filtered for extraction of DNA. Fluid was filtered on to a 47 mm Pall 0.2 micron membrane filter using a peristaltic pump. The filter holder was sterilized using 70% ethanol and the tubing was flushed with ~200 ml of milliQ water prior to filtering and in between samples. The fluid was filtered at a rate of 2L/hr. After filtering, ethanol sterilized tweezers were used to fold the filter and place in a 15 ml Falcon tube. The tube was immediately placed in the -80°C freezer. Throughout the course of the expedition, three negative control samples for contaminant screening were produced. These were produced by filtering 200 ml of milliQ water through the filter and freezing as described above.

Table 14. Squeezer Samples collected on Fkt2310602

Site	Dive	ID	Description
Dorado	530	49	#2
		50	#5 mixed with sediment
Unnamed E Caballito	536	157	Not logged
	536	159	Marker Q, Squeezer #9, near hole with green egg cement

Fkt230602 Cruise Report

Dorado	537	166	(not information logged)
		168	Marker W close to octopus
		169	#9 Marker R shimmering water
		170	#3 Marker R shimmering water
Unnamed E Caballito	538	185	#9 Marker Q in venting hole
		186	#3 Marker Q
Dorado Outcrop	542	272	#2 Marker A
		276	#9 Marker A sample mixed with seawater
		277	#5 Marker A sample mixed with seawater and particulates

Deployments & Recoveries summary

OsmoSamplers

Figure 5. OsmoSamplers recovered on Fkt230602

Recoveries: Two OsmoSamplers deployed in 2014 were recovered (Figure 5). OsmoSamplers were disassembled by Beth Orcutt and subsection by Beatriz Naranjo and Rachel Lauer.

The “white” OsmoSampler was recovered from Dorado Outcrop Marker W on Dive 530. It contained one Teflon coil + one 2-membrane pump. The intake was protected in a 0.5” tubing sheath and looked good. The intake line was not drained for sample collection (oops). The 2-membrane pump looked good, still salty. Fluid from the salt reservoir side was off the scale of the hand-held refractometer. The distilled water reservoir side gave a reading of 100 ppt. The Teflon coil was cut into 207x 1.5m sections, with the fluid collected into DNA-free (but not acid washed) 2ml tubes. Spot checking salinity on tubes #3 and #207 indicated seawater salinities.

The “black” OsmoSampler from Dorado Outcrop Marker R was collected on Dive 537. It also contained one Teflon coil + one 2-membrane pump. The intake was protected in a 0.5” tubing sheath and looked good. 2.75m of line from the intake tube to the Teflon coil was sectioned off and drained into tubes #1 and 2. The 2-membrane pump looked good, still salty. Fluid from the salt reservoir side was off the scale of the hand-held refractometer. The distilled water reservoir side gave a reading of 60 ppt. The

View of White OsmoSampler prior to recovery

View of the pump and coil from the White OsmoSampler that was recovered.

View of the Black OsmoSampler

Teflon coil was cut into 205x 1.5m sections, with the fluid collected into DNA-free (but not acid washed) 2ml tubes. Spot checking salinity on tubes #3 and #205 indicated seawater salinities.

Deployments (Figure 6): Two OsmoSamplers were assembled by Beth Orcutt for deployment at Dorado Outcrop. These systems both had one 200-300m Teflon coil and one 4-membrane pump. The first system was deployed at Dorado Outcrop on Dive 537 at Marker W (2023-06-14, 18:50). The “pink” system was deployed at unnamed outcrop E of Caballito on Dive 538 at Marker Q (2023-06-15, 16:04).

Figure 6. OsmoSamplers deployed on Fkt230602

Microbe Colonization Experiments (aka Microbe Traps)

Microbial colonization experiments were used to explore microbe-substrate interactions. A total of five microbial colonization experiments were deployed (Table 15, Figure 7). Each deployment consisted of duplicate microbial colonization chambers containing tens of grams of the following substrates: 23-million-year-old native basalt collected from Dorado Outcrop, 20-year-old native East Pacific Rise (EPR) basalt, mild steel, rhodochrosite, and glass wool (Figure 8). This experimental design facilitates testing the colonization preferences of seamount hydrothermal fluid microbial community members across various temporal, chemical, and spatial scales. Following recovery of these experiments, our goals are to use molecular sequencing approaches to explore the ecological roles that microbes, sourced from hydrothermal fluids, and their metabolisms and synergies play in the biogeochemical cycling of major elements of ecological and commercial interest (*e.g.*: carbon, nitrogen, iron, and manganese). Ultimately, four experiments were deployed at sites of hydrothermal venting (three sites at the Dorado Outcrop, and one at a new venting site discovered during this expedition at a seafloor feature east of a seamount known as “Caballito”) and one experiment was deployed as an environmental control at an abyssal lobate lava rock field site without any signs of hydrothermal fluid venting (Figure 9). All deployments were preloaded in BioBox 1 the evening before the dive. It is important to note that the biology experiment box often contained seawater from the previous day’s dive and that deployments were completely submerged in this water overnight prior to the ROV’s early morning deployments (Figure 10). We thank Dr. Roman Barco (University of Southern California) for discussions providing valuable insights into trap design, deployment strategies, and substrate selection during the early stages of this project; Dr. Wolfgang Bach (Universität Bremen) for providing aged Dorado Outcrop basalts (RS5_4782) collected in 2013/2014 on cruises led by Geoff Wheat; and Dr. Dan Fornari (WHOI) for providing a collection of East Pacific Rise Basalts including the 20-year-old glassy fresh basalt sample (AT11-7, EPR 9° 50’N) used in these experiments.

Table 15. Overview of Microbial Colonization Experiment deployments

Dive	Location
529	Dorado Outcrop Marker KW
530	Dorado Outcrop lobate lava field
536	Unnamed outcrop E Caballito Marker Q
537	Dorado Outcrop Marker R
542	Dorado Outcrop Marker A

Figure 7. Example of Microbe Colonization Experiments being deployed at Dorado Outcrop.

Figure 8. Overview of assembly of Microbe Colonization Experiments.

A) Large mineral samples were crushed with a hammer in “rock box”. B) Crushed and sieved (>200 μm size) basalt substrate. C) Mild Steel substrate and PVC cylinders undergoing UV exposure in clean hood. D) Sterilized Rhodochrosite substrate zipped tied in 6” by 6” 200 micron-polyethylene mesh bundles. E) Rhodochrosite bundles placed in PVC cylinders. F) Deployment configuration of PCV cylinders on dive weight with pre-wrapped polypropylene rope. G) Final configuration of a complete experiment deployment.

Figure 9. View of microbe colonization experiments on ROV SuBastian.

A) Placement of Biobox on basket (orange arrow). B) Biobox containing a substrate colonization experiment (note the color-coded substrates denoted by different color tape on rope endings). C) Top-down view of an Biobox experiment at a seamount venting site just before deployment.

Figure 10. Microbial colonization experiments at the seafloor

A) Dive 529, B) Dive 530, C) Dive 536, D) Dive 537, E) Dive 542.

Multibeam summary

The science party provided previously collected AUV Sentry and RV Atlantis bathymetric data to the RV Falkor (too) for several of the dive targets. Six new dedicated multibeam surveys with the RV Falkor (too)'s EM124 system were conducted during the expedition (Figure 11): two around Fuente Seamount (on 5 and 6 June) and four around Caballito Outcrop and an unnamed outcrop to the east (on 8, 10, 15, and 16 June). The new surveys were designed to be conducted between SuBastian dives assuming a maximum survey speed of 6-knots. Each of the new surveys targeted features at ~3000-m water depth, where the beam width is nominally 1-km. To ensure sufficient overlap in swath coverage, surveys were designed with a 500-m line spacing wherever possible, which reduced the potential for gaps in coverage due to ship roll, wind or current conditions. The images below present the planned survey lines to show what was targeted for coverage:

Figure 11. Screenshots of multibeam survey planning lines

Heat Flow and Temperature Logger summary

Background: The heat flow team was led by R. Lauer and R. Perrin from the University of Calgary, with considerable guidance and assistance at sea from B. Orcutt (Bigelow), J. Cortes (UCR), and the entire expedition team to ensure that planned measurements were compatible with the interdisciplinary expedition objectives. The primary goal of the heat flow program was to collect data that could be used to help constrain the patterns of fluid recharge and discharge within the network of seamounts and outcrops in this region. Wherever possible, heat flow transects were sited along existing seismic profiles to enable estimates of sediment thickness that facilitate further interpretation and modeling efforts. In some cases, heat flow targets were opportunistically collected on previously unexplored seamounts to add coverage to the heat flow database of the region. Following the expedition, we will use analytical and numerical modeling methods to determine the rates and patterns of fluid flow necessary to maintain the observed thermal conditions.

Methods: The primary tool for collecting new heat flow data was a 66-cm Alvin-style heat flow probe with five thermistors (spacing = 10 cm) and in-situ thermal conductivity capability. This instrument was operated from the SuBastian ROV using a Java-based graphical program that allowed setting of the probe measurement interval, power and timing of the heat pulse for thermal conductivity, and automated logging of formatted data. This program was developed at UCSC and has been successfully employed on Alvin (WHOI HOV) and ROV-based expeditions. The ROV team worked closely with the heat flow team to develop a system for mounting the probe on the side of Subastian, using a hydraulic ram rather than the manipulator to insert the probe into the sediment. This approach achieved two objectives: it created additional space on the “porch” or front of the sub for sample collection storage and ensured good thermal contact around the lance due to the smooth, vertical penetration of the sediment. Before each planned measurement, a long metal probe was inserted in the area adjacent to the planned penetration site to ensure sufficient sediment thickness for safe penetration of the lance and all five thermistors. Field estimates of heat flow were made using the following workflow:

1. Calculate the temperature difference between thermistors 1 and 5 and divide by the distance between them (0.4 m). The temperature difference was taken from the few measurements immediately before the heat pulse to approximate the equilibrium value as closely as we could using the field data.
2. Estimate thermal conductivity. For this value, we used estimates from ODP 170 (Kimura et al, 1997³), which show thermal conductivities in the upper 190 m of the sediments to range between approximately 0.7 and 0.9 W/m-K. We used 0.8 W/m-K in our estimates.
3. Calculate heat flow by multiplying the approximate thermal gradient (step 1) by the estimated thermal conductivity (step 2).

Final processing of the newly acquired data will require a careful assessment of data quality, sensor by sensor, and compilation of thermal conductivity values for use in deriving a subseafloor function to be used in lieu of direct measurements when the latter were not possible. In addition, careful analysis will be required for the assessment of several measurements which may indicate non-conductive conditions.

³ Kimura, G., E. Silver, and P. Blum (1997), Proceedings of the Ocean Drilling Program, Initial Reports, 458 pp., Ocean Drill. Program, College Station, Tex.

In addition, the UCSC team supplied five temperature loggers for deployment at vent sites to obtain a time series of vent temperatures from their deployment until their recovery in December (Table 16).

Table 16. Temperature logger deployment information

Temperature Logger S/N	Marker Tag	Latitude (°N)	Longitude	log interval	ROVit tag ID
768601	X	9.120659	-86.943576	30 min	
768602	A	9.088723	-87.101677	30 min	C
768600	W	9.082496	-87.095407	30 min	A
768604	Q	8.621199	-87.278773	30 min	
768616	R	9.082553	-87.095432	30 min	B

Results: A listing of heat flow measurement locations and other information is presented in Table 17, and a plot showing locations and preliminary heat flow estimates is shown in Figures 12-15. In total, thirty-eight heat flow measurements were made, with the majority located along transects corresponding to previously acquired seismic reflection lines that cross many of the outcrops in the region. A few measurements were made on the top or along steep slopes of the outcrop, where there was sufficient sediment to allow penetration of at least three of the probe's five thermistors.

Table 17. Summary of heat flow measurements.

Dive ID	Penetration ID	Date	Latitude ^a (°N)	Longitude ^a (°E)	Estimated gradient (K/m)	Estimated K (W/m-K)	Estimated heat flow (W/m ²)
531	1	05-Jun-23	8.750334	-87.200821	0.176	0.800	0.140
531	2	05-Jun-23	8.748568	-87.202278	0.150	0.800	0.119
531	3	05-Jun-23	8.747342	-87.203819	0.167	0.800	0.134
531	4	05-Jun-23	8.746187	-87.20472	0.201	0.800	0.161
531	5	05-Jun-23	8.745102	-87.20586	0.265	0.800	0.212
531	6	05-Jun-23	8.743774	-87.207126	0.245	0.800	0.195
531	7	05-Jun-23	8.743099	-87.207693	0.357	0.800	0.285
531	8	05-Jun-23	8.73698	-87.212883	0.270	0.800	0.179
531	9	06-Jun-23	8.736859	-87.212879	0.302	0.800	0.183
531	10	06-Jun-23	8.734463	-87.215134	0.267	0.800	0.173
531	11	06-Jun-23	8.733223	-87.216092	0.253	0.800	0.162
532	1	06-Jun-23	8.782586	-87.191973	0.116	0.800	0.074
532	2	06-Jun-23	8.790969	-87.163517	0.049	0.800	0.026
532	3	06-Jun-23	8.788107	-87.168143	0.120	0.800	0.072
535	1	11-Jun-23	8.625333	-87.282981	0.383	0.800	0.258
535	2	11-Jun-23	8.62486	-87.283725	0.514	0.800	0.334
535	4	11-Jun-23	8.624446	-87.284694	0.163	0.800	0.113
535	7	11-Jun-23	8.623899	-87.285969	0.189	0.800	0.122
535	8	11-Jun-23	8.624326	-87.287758	0.235	0.800	0.150
535	9	11-Jun-23	8.624113	-87.288033	0.229	0.800	0.152
538	1	15-Jun-23	8.620583	-87.276308	0.380	0.800	0.250
538	2	15-Jun-23	8.618861	-87.275451	0.403	0.800	0.261
538	3	15-Jun-23	8.618808	-87.274488	0.194	0.800	0.133
538	4	15-Jun-23	8.617668	-87.273841	0.222	0.800	0.135
539	1	16-Jun-23	8.617457	-87.314122	0.023	0.800	0.023
539	2	16-Jun-23	8.61696	-87.31496	0.032	0.800	0.020
539	3	16-Jun-23	8.6168	-87.31578	0.041	0.800	0.026
539	4	16-Jun-23	8.616617	-87.31669	0.041	0.800	0.026
539	5	16-Jun-23	8.61626	-87.31759	0.046	0.800	0.027
539	6	16-Jun-23	8.61612	-87.31846	0.075	0.800	0.047
539	7	16-Jun-23	8.61518	-87.32153	0.127	0.800	0.081
539	8	16-Jun-23	8.614998	-87.32233	0.151	0.800	0.096
539	9	16-Jun-23	8.614747	-87.32322	0.173	0.800	0.110

540	1	17-Jun-23	8.63611	-87.33268	0.033	0.800	0.021
540	2	17-Jun-23	8.63528	-87.33315	0.050	0.800	0.031
540	3	17-Jun-23	8.63447	-87.33361	0.077	0.800	0.049
540	4	17-Jun-23	8.63378	-87.33407	0.076	0.800	0.048
540	5	17-Jun-23	8.633	-87.33459	0.127	0.800	0.077
540	6	17-Jun-23	8.63234	-87.33508	0.109	0.800	0.070

^aMeasurement locations are rounded to nearest 0.0001°.

Figure 12. Preliminary results of heat flow measurements on unnamed outcrop SW of Fuente

Figure 13. Preliminary results of heat flow measurements on Fuente seamount.

Figure 14. Preliminary results of heat flow measurements on outcrop east of Caballito.

Figure 15. Preliminary results of heat flow measurements on Caballito outcrop.

Oceanographic observations and Hydrographic/Water sampling (i.e. CTD Niskin rosette casts, ADCP, EK80)

Background: The main objective of the oceanographic observation program was to characterize the hydrographic and hydrodynamic features in the study area, and to characterize the zooplankton diel vertical migration.

Methods: Water column sensing and sampling was conducted with a CTD-Rosette (SBE911/auxiliary sensors and Niskin bottles) launched from the vessel as well as a CTD mounted on ROV SuBastian. Currents and particulates were profiled with an Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler 300kHz/150kHz/38kHz and EK80 wide band echo sounder (38/70/120 kHz). CTD casts were named consecutively Fkt230602_CTD_#. ADCP were recording and logging during the whole cruise except when conducting bathymetric multibeam mapping. EK80 logging/recording was intermittently turned on at approximately 17:00 GMT-6 and then turned off at ~ 07:00 GMT-6. Absolute geostrophic velocity was visualized from AVISO servers to assess daily dynamics.

SOI CTD-Rosette system didn't show any inconsistency except for some spikes in the Conductivity sensor 1, but this was seen only in one cast. Because of the depth range, the PAR sensor was not used. The system used is a Sea-Bird Electronics 911plus CTD system on a rosette carrying 24 twelve-liter Niskin Bottles with:

Two temperature sensors (SBE 4)

Two conductivity sensors (SBE 3+)

Two dissolved oxygen sensors (SBE 43)

Fluorometer (chlorophyll a)/Turbidity Meter (WetLabs ECO FLNTUD)

Transmissometer (WetLabs C-star)

Altimeter

CTD data was processed according to the [Ocean Best Practices protocol](#), using the SBE Data Processing software with the following steps (PSA files can be found [here](#)):

1. Data Conversion
2. Window Filter
3. Filter
4. Derive TEOS-10

Figure 16. Map of the thirteen full-depth CTD locations on Fkt230602

Results: A total of 13 CTD casts were done to generate a preliminary assessment of hydrography and circulation during the expedition (Figure 16; with each cast shown in Figures XX). First, this time of year (May-June) is known locally as the transition time, this means that the ITCZ migrates from south to north, causing the shift from dry season to rainy season. This particular time of the year has not been well documented in terms of circulation patterns, but it is known that the signal of the Costa Rica Coastal Current is more evident during the second semester of the year. Based on the observations of this cruise, we observed a strong flow northward at the beginning of the cruise, with evidence of different water masses such as the Tropical Surface Water (TSW), Equatorial Surface Water (ESW), Thirteen degree water mass (13CW), Antarctic Intermediate Water (AAIW) and Lower Circumpolar Water (LCPW). The intrusion of the ESW around 50-100m deep was of particular interest, because it was evident in the first station at the trench but then the signal (based on T-S diagram, Figure 17) disappeared temporarily, to appear again towards the end of the cruise.

Figure 17. Temperature-Salinity Diagram of Stations 1 -13

The extent of the Oxygen Minimum Zone (OMZ) was evaluated in relation to the water masses, with a consistent association of the upper oxycline to the 13CW. There was also evidence of ventilation by water mass intrusions that remained to be determined, but we believe this also affected the thickness and depth of the anoxic core of the OMZ, which was shallower and narrower for the first stations and then became wider and deeper, below 500m. Based on altimetry data we determined our study area was under the influence of an anticyclonic gyre, that could have influenced the overall water column and the planktonic community distribution observed during ascents. This was confirmed by ADCP data.

Figure 18 - CTD001

Event/Station	001 (South of Trench)
File name	Fkt230602_CTD_001
Latitude	9.127°N
Longitude	85.288°W
Logger/Operator	Julianna D.
Start Date (UTC)	06022023
End Date (UTC)	06022023
Start Time (UTC)	10:15
End Time (UTC)	14:08
Start Date (Local)	06022023
End Date (Local)	06022023
Start Time (Local)	16:15
End Time (Local)	20:08
Niskin Bottle	NO NISKIN COLLECTED

Figure 19 - CTD002

Event/Station	002 (Dorado Outcrop)	
File name	FKt230602_CTD_002	
Latitude	9°4.926 N (9.082°N)	
Longitude	87° 5.725 W (87.095°W)	
Logger/Operator	Josh O Brien	
Start Date (UTC)	06032023	
End Date (UTC)	06032023	
Start Time (UTC)	04:08	
End Time (UTC)	07:35	
Start Date (Local)	06022023	
End Date (Local)	06032023	
Start Time (Local)	22:08	
End Time (Local)	01:35	
Niskin Bottle	9 bottles fired	
1,2,3	3000m	DIC/TA/NUTZ, MBIO (7.3L)
2	3000m	MBIO (9.5L)
3	3000m	
4	100m	phytoplankton
5	80m	phytoplankton
6	60m	phytoplankton
7	40m	phytoplankton
8	20m	phytoplankton
9	1.63m	DIC/TA/NUTZ

Figure 20 - CTD003

Event/Station	003 (HydroMidN)	
File name	FKt230602_CTD_003	
Latitude	9° 5.66730 N (9.094°N)	
Longitude	87° 1.21808 W (87.02 °W)	
Logger/Operator	Josh O Brien	
Start Date (UTC)	06042023	
End Date (UTC)	06042023	
Start Time (UTC)	02:04	
End Time (UTC)	05:03	
Start Date (Local)	06032023	
End Date (Local)	06032023	
Start Time (Local)	08:04	
End Time (Local)	23:03	
Niskin Bottle	1 bottle fired	
1	2m	DIC/TA/NUTZ

Figure 21 - CTD004

Event/Station	004 (unnamed outcrop SW of Fuente)	
File name	Fkt230602_CTD_004	
Latitude	8° 44.43736' N (8.741 °N)	
Longitude	87° 1.21808 W (87.209°W)	
Logger/Operator	Steph	
Start Date (UTC)	06052023	
End Date (UTC)	06052023	
Start Time (UTC)	10:59	
End Time (UTC)	13:54	
Start Date (Local)	06052023	
End Date (Local)	06052023	
Start Time (Local)	04:59	
End Time (Local)	07:54	
Niskin Bottle	6 bottles fired	
1	100m	phytoplankton
2	80m	phytoplankton
3	60m	phytoplankton
4	40m	phytoplankton
5	20m	phytoplankton
6	1.4m	DIC/TZ/NUTZ, microplastics

Figure 22 - CTD005

Event/Station	005 (HydroNW)	
File name	FKt230602_CTD_005	
Latitude	9° 14.51395 N (9.242°N)	
Longitude	86° 59.7648 W (86.996 °W)	
Logger/Operator	Josh O Brien	
Start Date (UTC)	06102023	
End Date (UTC)	06102023	
Start Time (UTC)	00:57	
End Time (UTC)	03:29	
Start Date (Local)	06092023	
End Date (Local)	06092023	
Start Time (Local)	18:57	
End Time (Local)	21:29	
Niskin Bottle	1 bottle fired	
1	1.943m	DIC/TA/NUTZ, microplastics

Figure 23 - CTD006

Event/Station	006 (HydroSW)	
File name	FKt230602_CTD_006	
Latitude	8° 48.65624 N (8.811°N)	
Longitude	87° 19.45600 W (87.324 °W)	
Logger/Operator	Josh O Brien / Jimbo	
Start Date (UTC)	06122023	
End Date (UTC)	06122023	
Start Time (UTC)	00:51	
End Time (UTC)	03:33	
Start Date (Local)	06112023	
End Date (Local)	06112023	
Start Time (Local)	18:52	
End Time (Local)	21:33	
Niskin Bottle	1 bottle fired	
1	1.532m	DIC/TA/NUTZ, microplastics

Figure 24 - CTD007

Event/Station	007 (E of Caballito)	
File name	FKt230602_CTD_007	
Latitude	8.620052° N	
Longitude	87.306762° W	
Logger/Operator	Josh O'Brien	
Start Date (UTC)	06122023	
End Date (UTC)	06122023	
Start Time (UTC)	05:42	
End Time (UTC)	08:27	
Start Date (Local)	06112023	
End Date (Local)	06122023	
Start Time (Local)	11:42	
End Time (Local)	02:27	
Niskin Bottle	1 bottle fired	
1	1.83m	DIC/TA/NUTZ, microplastics

Figure 25 - CTD008

Event/Station	008 (HydroCenter)	
File name	FKt230602_CTD_008	
Latitude	8°59.157' N (8.62°N)	
Longitude	87°6.153' W (87.307°W)	
Logger/Operator	Julianna / Josh	
Start Date (UTC)	06152023	
End Date (UTC)	06152023	
Start Time (UTC)	04:26	
End Time (UTC)	07:16	
Start Date (Local)	06142023	
End Date (Local)	06152023	
Start Time (Local)	22:26	
End Time (Local)	01:16	
Niskin Bottle	1 bottle fired	
1	1.573m	DIC/TA/NUTZ, microplastics

Figure 26 - CTD009

Event/Station	009 (HydroMidS)	
File name	FKt230602_CTD_009	
Latitude	8.0967°N	
Longitude	87.1785°W	
Logger/Operator	Julianna	
Start Date (UTC)	06182023	
End Date (UTC)	06182023	
Start Time (UTC)	06:10	
End Time (UTC)	08:45	
Start Date (Local)	06182023	
End Date (Local)	06182023	
Start Time (Local)	00:10	
End Time (Local)	02:45	
Niskin Bottle	1 bottle fired	
1	1.9m	DIC/TA/NUTZ, microplastics

Figure 27 - CTD010

Event/Station	010 (Tengosed)	
File name	Fkt230602_CTD_010	
Latitude	9.131722° N	
Longitude	86.942409° W	
Logger/Operator	Josh O Brien	
Start Date (UTC)	06192023	
End Date (UTC)	06192023	
Start Time (UTC)	03:35	
End Time (UTC)	05:27	
Start Date (Local)	06182023	
End Date (Local)	06182023	
Start Time (Local)	21:35	
End Time (Local)	23:27	
Niskin Bottle	1 bottle fired	
1	1.840m	DIC/TA/NUTZ, microplastics

Figure 28 - CTD011

Event/Station	011 (HydroMidW)	
File name	FKt230602_CTD_011	
Latitude	9.010639° N	
Longitude	87.160763° W	
Logger/Operator	Josh O Brien	
Start Date (UTC)	06202023	
End Date (UTC)	06202023	
Start Time (UTC)	04:41	
End Time (UTC)	07:20	
Start Date (Local)	06192023	
End Date (Local)	06202023	
Start Time (Local)	20:41	
End Time (Local)	01:20	
Niskin Bottle	1 bottle fired	
1	1.787m	DIC/TA/NUTZ, microplastics

Figure 29 - CTD012

Event/Station	012 (HydroMidE)	
File name	Fkt230602_CTD_012	
Latitude	8° 56.61530' N (8.943°N)	
Longitude	87° 2.3233' W (87.039°W)	
Logger/Operator	Steph	
Start Date (UTC)	06202023	
End Date (UTC)	06202023	
Start Time (UTC)	08:44	
End Time (UTC)	11:20	
Start Date (Local)	06202023	
End Date (Local)	06202023	
Start Time (Local)	02:44	
End Time (Local)	05:20	
Niskin Bottle	1 bottle fired	
1	1.374m	DIC/TA/NUTZ, microplastics

Figure 30 - CTD013

Event/Station	013 (South of Trench)	
File name	FKt230602_CTD_013	
Latitude	9.168591° N	
Longitude	85.650345° W	
Logger/Operator	Josh O Brien	
Start Date (UTC)	06202023	
End Date (UTC)	06212023	
Start Time (UTC)	21:44	
End Time (UTC)	01:10	
Start Date (Local)	06202023	
End Date (Local)	06202023	
Start Time (Local)	15:44	
End Time (Local)	19:10	
Niskin Bottle	3 bottles fired	
1	3674m	DIC/TA/NUTZ, microplastics
2	3674m	Stored for shorebased standards
3	1.8m	DIC/TA/NUTZ, microplastics

Figure 31 - Summarized results from ADCP

ADCP figures showing the formation and progression of anticyclonic eddy

Figure 32 - Summarized results from altimetry data (AVISO).

Absolute geostrophic velocity vectors from AVISO altimetry data showing the formation and progression of anticyclonic eddy

Fkt230602 Cruise Report

Water Samples – ROV SuBastian

Twenty eight (28) ROV Niskin water samples were collected (Table 18). 5L and 2.5L niskin bottles were mounted on the side of the ROV for collecting bottom seawater near areas of operation. Samples for cell counts consisted of 14ml of sample fixed with 0.875 ml of 32% paraformaldehyde, these were stored cold. The remaining fluids in these bottles were stored in 10L cubitainers and then filtered through 0.22 μ m Sterivex.

Table 18. ROV Niskin water samples collected

Dive	Bottle	Sample	Purpose
529	5	24	DIC/TA/NUTZ
529	2	11	Cell counts, DNA
529	3	23	Cell counts, DNA, exposure experiment
530	5	48	DIC/TA/NUTZ
530	6	32	DIC/TA/NUTZ
530	1	31	Cell counts, DNA, exposure experiment
530	2	47	Cell counts, DNA
531	4	71	DIC/TA/NUTZ, cell counts, DNA, exposure experiment
532	5	93	DIC/TA/NUTZ
532	1	92	Cell counts, DNA, exposure experiment
533	6	122	DIC/TA/NUTZ

Fkt230602 Cruise Report

533	1	121	Cell counts, DNA, exposure experiment
534	5	133	DIC/TA/NUTZ
534	6	141	DIC/TA/NUTZ
534	3	140	Cell counts, DNA,
534	4	132	Cell counts, DNA,
535	5	145	DIC/TA/NUTZ
535	1	146	Cell counts, DNA, exposure experiment
537	5	174	DIC/TA/NUTZ
537	1	173	Cell counts, DNA
538	5	187	DIC/TA/NUTZ
538	6	193	DIC/TA/NUTZ
538	3	194	Cell counts, DNA
538	4	188	Cell counts, DNA, exposure experiment
540	5	233	DIC/TA/NUTZ
540	1	232	Cell counts, DNA
541	5	262	DIC/TA/NUTZ
541	4	263	Cell counts, DNA

Outreach

The Fkt230602 outreach program consisted of numerous elements: artists at sea, blogs, livestream and social media engagement, ship-to-shore engagements, video products, press, and ship tours during demobilization.

Artists at Sea

Figure 33. Carlos Hiller (background) and Michel Droge (foreground) were Artists-At-Sea on the Octopus Odyssey Fkt230602 expedition.

Figure 34. Both artists created numerous paintings during the expedition. some of which were made using paints mixed with residual sediment and/or rock samples collected during the ROV dives. Both artists used social media (i.e. Instagram) to engage global audiences.

Michel Droge

Michel created paintings and sketches at sea and captured sound and video recordings for an upcoming multimedia exhibition (Tables 19, 20).

Table 19. Nine paintings created © Michel Droge 2023, on temporary loan to Jorge Cortes for exhibit in Costa Rica.

Anemone, oil on wood panel,	Octopus Odyssey, oil on	Newly hatched octopus
-----------------------------	-------------------------	-----------------------

<p>6x6</p>		
<p>Deep seascape, oil on canvas, 36"x48"</p>		
<p>To Dance in Deep Waters, oil on canvas, 10"x8"</p>	<p>Cockatoo Squid oil on canvas 8"x10"</p>	<p>Volcanic Deep Sea with oil volcanic rock pigment, 6"x6"</p>

Table 20. Watercolors and sketches © Michel Droge 2023

Carlos Hiller

Table 21. Paintings created © Carlos Hiller 2023.

<p>Contemplando al Abismo</p>		
<p>Hogar de Cristal</p>	<p>Lluvia Pelágica</p>	

Maternidad Adorado

Blogs

The science party contributed eight blogs during the course of the expedition for posting on the SOI website. All of these were translated into both English and Spanish, with Beatriz Naranjo

contributing all translations. This was done to foster cross-cultural understanding and appreciation.

- [June 6](#) - Beth Orcutt and Jorge Cortés - Returning to the Dorado Outcrop
- [June 10](#) - Rachel Lauer and Rob Perrin - Fluid flow through the crust
- [June 12](#) - Janet Voight and Holly Lutz - Discovering new species and exploring deep-sea microbiomes
- [June 16](#) - Sergio Cambronero - Todo está conectado
- [June 18](#) - Wendy Matamoros - Deep-sea exploration in Latin America
- [June 23](#) - Carlos Hiller - Los Colores de la Ciencia
- [June 29](#) - Michel Droge - Art & Science with Octopus Odyssey
- [July 27](#) - Maila Guilhon and Diva Amon - Working towards equitable deep-ocean research

Livestream and social media engagement

SOI reported the following engagement statistics for their social media channels (thanks to Alex Ingel for editing videos!!):

- Facebook: 4M engagements (likes, shared, comments; 10.8M impressions (saw but did not engage); **8M video views**
- Twitter: 30k engagements, 509k impressions, 66k video views
- Instagram: 32 posts (15 reels + 17 photos), **3.6M video views**, 436k engagements
 - [Tripod fish reel \(3M views\)](#)
 - [Dumbo octopus](#) reel
 - [Octopus closeup](#) reel
 - [Male octopus showoff](#) reel
 - [World Ocean Day octopus baby](#) reel
 - [Sergio's "woah" isopod](#) reel
 - [Snipe eel](#) reel
 - [Glass squid](#) reel
 - [Carlos'](#) reel
 - [Michel's](#) reel
- YouTube: 5 video products + 14 dive livestreams, 45k views of livestream (Costa Rica second largest audience comprising 8.2% of viewership), 130k views of produced videos

Video Products

- [Week 1 - Odyssey Origins](#) (6.7k views)
- [Week 2 - Al País de Aguas Profundas](#) (1.7k views)
- [Week 3 - An Impressive Wealth](#) (79k views)
- [Science Story - Faith in Independent Thinking \(ft. Gustavo Ramirez\)](#) (557 views)
- [4K highlights](#) (41k views)

Ship to Shore Engagements

The science party participated in 10 ship-to-shore engagements with diverse audiences, conducting the majority of these (7 of 10) in Spanish with school student audiences in Costa Rica (Table 22). At least 780 people participated in these events, and they were well-received. An example comment: *“Thank you very much for the invitation to participate in this highly prestigious event. My students were very happy and excited about this experience. If in the future our Scientific High School students can be considered again for events like these, I am sure it will be a great success, as it is part of their continuous education prior to making vocational decisions. Among our students, there are many young people with aspirations to become naval engineers, mechanical engineers, biologists, marine biologists, doctors, biotechnologists, and professionals in many other areas of knowledge.”* -Roberto de Jesús Mora Sánchez (Región Brunca-Pérez Zeledón Scientific High School)

Table 22. Ship-to-Shore engagements during Fkt230602

Date	Group	Audience + Size	Science party involved	Language
June 2	Bishop Museum, HI, USA	Adults, 86	Diva, Beth	English
June 6	Colegio Cientifico de Costa Rica, CR	High school, 60	Sergio, Celeste	Spanish
June 7	Dolphins Academy, CR	High school, 28	Carlos, Celeste, Sergio	Spanish
June 8	Field Museum, USA	All ages, 20	Janet, Holly	English
June 10	Gulf Research Institute (Texas), USA	High school. 50	Gus, Sergio	English and Spanish
June 12	Explore by the Seat of your Pants, USA	Middle-High school, 416	Rachel, Gus	English
June 14	UNED ⁴ scientific high schools (sncccr.ed.cr), CR: San Pedro Scientific High School (San José Province) San Ramón Scientific High School (Alajuela Province); Puntarenas Scientific High School (Puntarenas Province); Cartago Scientific High School (Cartago Province); Región Brunca-Pérez Zeledón Scientific High School (San José Province); Guanacaste Scientific High School (Guanacaste Province)	High school, 40	Beatriz, Sergio	Spanish
June 16	UNED public academic high schools from rural areas, CR - Liceo de Tarrazú (San José Province); Liceo de Cuajiniquil (Guanacaste Province); Liceo de Palmar Norte (Puntarenas Province)	High school, 48	Beatriz, Celeste	Spanish
June 19	UNED scientific high schools, CR - - Atlantic Scientific High School (Limón Province); Alajuela Scientific High School (Alajuela Province); San Vito Scientific High School (Puntarenas Province)	High school, 80	Beatriz, Sergio	Spanish
June 20	Colegio Metropolitano, Venezuela	Middle school, 10	Carlos	Spanish

⁴ UNED, Universidad Estatal a Distancia, www.uned.ac.cr

Notable Press

SOI Press release - garnered at least 725 articles published in 45 countries:

<https://schmidtocean.org/scientists-discover-new-deep-sea-octopus-nurseries-in-costa-rica/>

Notable popular press coverage:

- Canada:
 - CBC Calgary interview by Andrew Brown with Rachel Lauer (20 June 2023)
 - CBC [As It Happens interview](#) by Nik Koksall with Beth Orcutt (4 July 2023)
 - CBC Radio show [The Home Stretch interview](#) (11 July 2023)
 - UCalgary [feature](#) (9 Aug 2023)
 - CBC [Quirks & Quarks podcast](#) interview with Rachel Lauer (15 Sept 2023)
- Costa Rica + Latin America:
 - [Costa Rica Hoy \(30 June 2023\)](#)
 - [Delfino \(13 June 2023\)](#)
 - [El Observador \(25 June 2023\)](#)
 - [La Nación \(16 July 2023\)](#)
 - [La Nación \(6 July 2023\)](#)
 - [Ojo al Clima \(16 May 2023\)](#)
 - [Pablo Cartín facebook \(10 July 2023\)](#)
 - [UCR press release \(17 July 2023\)](#)
 - Mexico: [INVDES.COM \(6 July 2023\)](#)
 - [NatGeo En Espanol \(6 July 2023\)](#)
 - [Codigo Oculto about eel \(7 July 2023\)](#) - **shared 2564 times, 2nd most of expedition**
- USA based:
 - [ABC News \(30 June 2023\)](#)
 - [Axios newsletter \(29 June 2023\):](#)
 - [CBS News \(3 July 2023\)](#)
 - CNN:
 - <https://www.cnn.com/2023/06/30/americas/octopus-nursery-deep-sea-discovery-scn/index.html> - **shared over 8400 times, most of expedition**
 - <https://www.cnn.com/videos/world/2023/06/29/octopus-nursery-discovered-deep-sea-costa-rica-cprog-orig-aw.cnn>
 - [Fox Weather \(30 June 2023\)](#)
 - [Gizmodo \(29 June 2023\)](#)
 - [IFLScience \(30 June 2023\)](#)
 - [Interesting Engineering \(30 June 2023\)](#)
 - [LiveScience/Yahoo \(29 June 2023\)](#)
 - [The Messenger \(30 June 2023\)](#)
 - [Mashable \(1 July 2023\)](#)
 - [MongaBay \(4 July 2023\)](#)
 - [National Geographic \(7 July 2023\)](#)
 - [Nautilus \(5 October 2023\)](#)

- [Notes from the Deep interview with Michel Droge \(9 Oct 2023\)](#)
- [NPR \(3 July 2023\)](#)
- [Sacramento Bee \(29 June 2023\)](#)
- [Salon \(12 Oct 2023\)](#) - skate nursery coverage
- [Science Alert \(4 July 2023\)](#)
- [Scientific American article \(3 July 2023\)](#)
- [Smithsonian \(3 July 2023\)](#)
- [Sky News \(30 June 2023\)](#)
- [USA Today \(3 July 2023\)](#)
- [WION \(30 June 2023\)](#)
- [Yahoo!News \(3 July 2023\)](#)
- [CalState Los Angeles Press Release](#)
- EU/UK based:
 - [AOL \(29 June 2023\)](#)
 - [Independent \(29 June 2023\)](#)
 - [La Vanguardia \(6 July 2023\)](#)
 - [Infobae \(4 July 2023\)](#)
 - [Kopalniawiedzy \(4 July 2023\)](#)
- Global:
 - [India Today \(5 July 2023\)](#)
 - [Karapaia \(5 July 2023\)](#)
 - [Hindustan Times \(2 July 2023\)](#)

Ship tours during demobilization

Upon returning to port on 21 June 2023, we conducted two tours for government ministry and NGO representatives as well as faculty and students of regional universities upon returning to port on 21 June 2023 (Table 23).

Table 23. Tour guests from Costa Rica during Fkt230602

Type	Institution	Guests
Academic	University of Costa Rica	Guaria Cardenes, Director School of Geology Valentin Chesnel Zehr, School of Geology Álvaro Morales, Director CIMAR Marco Barahona, Director Geology Graduate Program Maximiliano Garnier Villarreal, School of Geology Stephanie Murillo Maikut, School of Geology Viviana Gamboa Sojo, School of Geology Fiorella Vásquez, School of Biology Sofía Gutiérrez Rodríguez, School of Biology Ingrid Rodríguez Wolter Leoanardo Chacón, School of Biology

		Arturo Angulo Sibaja, School of Biology Sofía Cortés-Mesén, Coastal Zone Management Program
Academic	Open University of Costa Rica	Esteban José Daniels Chan, Coordinator Technical Schools
Govt	US Embassy in Costa Rica	Emilia Alfaro, Environment Division Andrea Muñoz, Environment Division
NGO	IUCN, Central America	Rocío Córdoba, Ecosystem Commission

Capacity Sharing & Best Practices Research

The perceptions of the science party in relation to the planning, development and execution of deep-ocean and open-ocean expeditions will be analyzed under the lens of international collaborative approaches, with 'Octopus Odyssey' used as a case study. Participants voluntarily shared their impressions, which will be used to support a co-developed peer-reviewed commentary publication that reflects pathways towards equitable international collaboration.

